

A COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT METHODOLOGY: resources, reflections, recommendations

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Table of contents

Heritage & legacies.....	4
DE-BIAS: outline and outcomes.....	4
Power struggles.....	4
Methodology: scope & content.....	5
Setting the scene.....	7
Identities, heritage, values.....	7
Cultural policies in Europe: a bird's eye view.....	11
Policy models.....	11
The role of the European Union.....	18
Audience development?.....	21
The power of words.....	28
Problematic metadata.....	28
Dynamics of meaning.....	29
Sectoral strategies.....	30
The DE-BIAS approach.....	30
Engagement methodologies.....	33
Meeting with empathy, circulating meanings.....	33
Open dialogue.....	34
Empathic processes.....	35
Asymmetry and heterogeneity.....	36
Methodological focus on storytelling.....	38
Definition and value proposition.....	38
Thinking caps.....	39
Stories as communication.....	40
Paradigms for postmodern times.....	40
Educational practices in GLAMs.....	42
Blueprint of a storytelling workshop.....	42
Good practices: community engagement projects.....	44
More good practices: published methodologies.....	47
Routes to reflection: proposed approach for DE-BIAS community work.....	55
Table of elements.....	56
Signposts for thoughtful engagement.....	61
Signpost 1: Nourish the intercultural dialogue.....	61
Signpost 2: Community pivots.....	64
Signpost 3: Follow-up, feedback and give back.....	67
Closing the loop: communities and cultural heritage as a common good.....	69
Bibliographical references.....	72

HERITAGE & LEGACIES

Heritage & legacies

When it comes to expressions and terms widely used in professional life - say, for the case of argument 'methodology' - it can be refreshing to go back to their very roots in an aim to bypass 'project jargon'. And so, at the very outset of the exercise of which you'll find a reflection and substantiation in the present publication, we found ourselves going back to what a 'methodology' actually entails. The meanings vary in emphasis and scope, beginning with the study of different methods - rather a comparative approach - but also possibly referring to those very methods themselves. Interestingly, we saw our aspirations of what this document could be not only mirrored in both definitions but also in a third dimension: that in which the 'logos' in methodology is highlighted and refers to the philosophical discussion of background assumptions. This definition, too, echoes key issues and considerations that are at the very crux of the project to which this report hopes to make a relevant contribution: DE-BIAS - Detecting and cur(at)ing harmful language in cultural heritage collections.

DE-BIAS: outline and outcomes

DE-BIAS is a two-year project funded under the [Digital Europe Programme](#) and carried out by an 11 partner consortium, aiming to promote a more inclusive and up-to-date approach to describing cultural collections. A core component of DE-BIAS is a newly assembled and case-specific tool that automatically detects offensive terms and provides information on their problematic background. The 'food' of the AI-powered tool will consist of a vocabulary pairing biased language with contextual information and suggestions for appropriate terms. That thesaurus, in turn, will be co-created by project partners and groups of representatives of 4 specific communities. This pilot action in the short term wants to inspire replicable models and formats of interaction and - with a view to a more distant future - hopes to contribute to a paradigm shift towards a heritage sector where inclusive, respectful and representative metadata are the new normal.

As a final outcome, the tool operating on the basis of the thesaurus will be integrated into Europeana website and made available for use by individual cultural heritage institutions to analyse and detect bias in their own datasets. Finally, the project will develop capacity-building resources, including an online knowledge base and train-the-trainer course, to ensure the long-term impact and adoption of project results by the cultural heritage sector.

Power struggles

The project was co-designed and co-written by a group of organisations - including aggregators of digital cultural collections, university and technical partners as well as community engagement experts - that shared a certain discomfort about how stereotypical, hurtful or inappropriate language often comes with digital objects as an unwanted and heavy load of luggage.

While being passionate about finding a solution together with historically disadvantaged heritage communities, the partnership also immediately recognised the complexity of

entering that dialogue with said communities on eye-level. In other words: how could community connections, contributions and genuine co-steering be accomplished with 'equality' as a common driver?

While the project team is wholeheartedly committed to operating in a conversation space of equilibrium, social justice, democracy and polyvocality, it also acknowledges that the preconditions for projects like these are not ideal as a backdrop for efforts towards the redistribution of powers. It is part of project reality that power dynamics are indeed at play and that any attempt to recalibrate decision making mechanisms can manifest only within the blueprint provided by the policies and funding programs that apply.

Together with the establishment of an external project Advisory Board, an internal Community Engagement Working Group with representatives of all work packages, the establishment of a DE-BIAS grant to support community contributions and a series of 'sensemaking sessions' intended to sharpen the consortium's insights into the nature and manifestations of bias and best practices in working with communities, the present methodology document forms part of the mitigation strategy the project team has put in place. Realising that, still, we'll need to stay alert and conscious of power dynamics throughout the project journey, we hope that by sharing a ground set of methodological baselines and principles, our work with regards to community engagement will be genuinely of a reciprocal nature and benefit the community stakeholders as well as DE-BIAS.

Methodology: scope & content

This document was conceived as a blueprint for community engagement activities in the realm of the DE-BIAS project, to be used by partners while designing, preparing and conducting their online and onsite events. In its current form - a third document iteration - it is also intended as a resource and a support to other organisations wishing to replicate (parts of) the present methodological setup to ensure an inclusive, safe, and trust-based approach for the implementation of co-creation activities with communities.

In this resource, prospective as well as experienced organisations will find a framework for conceptualising, planning and evaluating their community engagement activities as topics discussed include: the role of heritage in shaping identities; the process of value creation within the cultural field; the development of European cultural policies in the last decades; the role of Audience Development in fostering access and participation in cultural activities for broader societal groups; examples of specific methodologies and tools to engage communities.

True to the spirit and the core principles of the DE-BIAS project, this Methodology is not intended to serve as a one-size-fits-all manual or a set of rules carved in stone. The very essence of working with communities is fostering an approach based on openness, reciprocal dynamics, flexibility and individually tailored modes of collaboration. Therefore any methodological underpinning of community work can never be a static roadmap but rather a supporting offer of signposts, milestones and directions of travel.

SETTING THE SCENE

Setting the scene

Identities, heritage, values

Culture is a term that is very wide and often contested, with academics recording many variations in meaning: a universally accepted definition of it does not exist and probably never will. Underpinning the notion of culture is the idea that the concept itself is dynamic and changes over time and in different contexts, resulting in many people today identifying with one or more cultures and many different groups.

Culture is a defining feature of a person's identity, contributing to how they see themselves and the groups with which they identify. A person's understanding of their own and other's identities develops from birth and is shaped by the values and attitudes prevalent at home and in the surrounding community. Like that of culture, also the notion of identity is complex, with people's identity or identities becoming more complex over time as they interact with different groups. Identity adapts due to many factors including mass media, popular culture and increased opportunities for social interaction facilitated by new technologies. These factors, together with globalisation, migration and inter-marriage between people from different cultural backgrounds, means that people are more and more often identifying with multiple cultures.

How do these very complex notions relate to that of heritage? The notion of heritage is undoubtedly linked to that of culture and identity: heritage is the legacy that we receive from the past, that we experience in the present and that we will pass on to future generations. Through the 1972 Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, UNESCO established that certain places on Earth have "exceptional universal value," belong to the shared heritage of humanity and are an irreplaceable source of life and inspiration. However, CH is not limited to monuments and collections of objects. It also includes lived expressions inherited from our ancestors and passed on to our descendants. These include oral traditions, performing arts, social manners, rituals, celebrations, practices and knowledge and techniques related to traditional handcrafts. Despite its fragility, intangible CH or living heritage is an important factor in maintaining cultural diversity.

The association between heritage and identity is well established in the heritage literature. Heritage is assumed to provide a physical representation and reality to the ephemeral and slippery concept of 'identity'. As the notions of culture and identities, also that of CH is a dynamic one: it is based on values associated to it, values which change and shift according to political and societal changes¹.

¹ This concept has been introduced as a milestone in cultural policy in 2005 by the Council of Europe in its Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society (Faro Convention). Art. 2 affirms that "cultural heritage is a group of resources inherited from the past which people identify, independently of ownership, as a reflection and expression of their constantly evolving values, beliefs, knowledge and traditions. [...] A heritage community consists of people who value specific aspects of cultural heritage which they wish, within the framework of public action, to sustain and transmit to future generations" (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list//conventions/treaty/199>).

The values connected to heritage are multiple and, while the definition of the concept of CH is established *ex lege*, the definitions of its associated values are even more complicated². Values are the result of a social construction taking place in every community in every age: this is valid for all objects of an evaluation and consequently also for CH. But even if we admit that “every value is a symbolic value”³, it remains to be established how the values associated with heritage are constructed.

We can start from the concept of the economic value of CH, since the analysis of this specific kind of value has important implications on the social value of heritage. It is a multidimensional value, defined as Total Economic Value (TEV), used to describe the total value of non-reproducible resources. It is the sum of the value of its use (direct and indirect) and the value independent of its use, to which option value, bequest value and existence value are attributable.

Given that, as far as CH is concerned, it is not possible to use the replacement cost as an indicator of the value of the asset: the benefit value is used for this purpose – that is, the utility of the cultural object for the users. It is useful to underscore the definition of the so-called social and psychological benefits, which refer to the sphere of social relationships, to the level of quality of life, and to the state of inner wellbeing that arises from the possibility of living in the presence of (and making use of) a high environmental and cultural standard. Social benefits include:

- increase in the cultural level of people;
- enhancement of cultural diversity and collective memory in every community;
- increase in individual technical skills;
- awareness of existential and environmental problems;
- raise of the quality of life;
- crime reduction;
- social relations;
- awareness of civil rights.

But if the recognition and evaluation of these benefits are less problematic with regards to issues of conservation and re-use of historical-architectural heritage – also because in this area there are well-established methodological practices for research and evaluation – their assessment becomes more complicated in the instance of the use of CH (understood as museums, galleries, archaeological areas) and participation in artistic and cultural activities. In this case, we speak of community benefits, which suggest that the improvement of an individual’s cultural baggage can lead to the dissemination of positive effects for the benefit of the entire community. In particular, community benefits can have on the one hand, this

² This chapter is largely taken from C. Da Milano, “Values as anchor” in C. Da Milano, E. Falchetti, M.F. Guida (eds.), *Intercultural Rehearsals*, Editrice Bibliografica, Milano 2019, pp. 157-164.

³ S. Pearce, *On Collecting: An Investigation into Collecting in the European Tradition*, Routledge, London 1995, p. 285.

specific moral/educational character, while on the other hand they can be linked to themes such as the development of a critical conscience in individuals and their ability to construct their own cultural identity.

But continuing to talk about values associated with heritage, we arrive at aesthetic, cognitive and political values. In Western culture, pairs of opposing concepts determine mental and emotional values, as well as value judgments on culture (Fig. 1). On the left are the aspects embraced by European culture: in fact, we prefer that which is real with respect to what is not; we feel at ease with what is normal, known and identifiable. We prefer interesting things, and we know what art is, believing that this notion is closely linked to the concepts of “importance” and “masterpiece.” By widening the angle from which we observe it, this diagram becomes the representation of a wider contrast between “us” (which we represent as normality, authenticity, importance) and “them” (understood as carriers of non -culture, abnormality, falsehood), thus also assuming a political value. Obviously, within society these aesthetic, cognitive and political values are intertwined and it is very difficult to distinguish one from the other and to understand the mechanisms according to which they operate.

Us	Them
Present	Past
Authentic	Inauthentic
Known	Unknown
Normal	Strange
Art	Non-art
True	False
Extraordinary	Ordinary
Interesting	Boring
Comprehensible	Incomprehensible
Masterpiece	Artefact

Fig. 1: Pairs of opposing concepts that generate the traditional value judgements on culture (source: author's illustration from S. Pearce, On Collecting: An Investigation into Collecting in the European Tradition, Routledge, London 1995, p. 285)

The perception of value is also an appropriation, a way of doing something by distancing ourselves from something else (the separation between “us” and “them”). This distance is a cultural distance that operates in the two dimensions of time and space: in both cases, according to our cultural tradition, a line exists that leads us to consider what is above it as being close and similar, and what is below it as distant and foreign.

Among the pairs of opposites that form the value judgments on culture within the European tradition, the first to be indicated is “us” : “them” = “European” : “non-European”. It is clear indeed that the recognition of oneself occurs through identification of what is different from

us: even if this is true for all human beings, for Europeans this way of conceiving the world is more accentuated and has given rise to this system of dichotomies on which it is based⁴.

The differences that constitute the essence of “us” and “others” can be identified on two main axes: the spatial and the temporal (Fig. 2). The meeting point between the two axes represents the individual: within a certain distance from this, both along the time axes and along the space axes, there is all that is familiar and belongs to us (family, city, language, uses and customs, somatic characteristics, religion), while as we move away we find what is “different” which becomes more alien the greater the distance from the meeting point of the two axes. Having crossed the line of demarcation within which we are “us” Europeans, we encounter “the others” in a crescendo of geographical and temporal diversity, which lie beyond us in geographical terms and before us in temporal terms.

Fig. 2: Differences and distances on the space and time axes between US and THEM
(source: S. Pearce, *op. cit.*, Routledge, London 1995, p. 313)

Let’s try now to analyse the values of heritage from a post-structuralist perspective. We know that heritage is evaluated according to extremely different parameters, depending on the subjective judgement of individuals or groups of individuals. Writers like Barthes, Foucault and Bourdieau have de-legitimised the idea that value judgments are valid, suggesting that they

⁴ Historically speaking, in the European world this has happened with the Greeks who pit themselves against the barbarians, then with the Romans –bearers of the concept of *Romanitas*, who challenged those who did not adhere to it, then with the opposition between Christians and non -Christians, and finally, starting from the second half of the fifteenth century, with the confrontation between Europeans and inhabitants of the new worlds that were gradually being discovered and then colonised.

do not actually reflect objective truths, but simply the image of man who, believing that he observes the outside world, actually observes his own image reflected in a mirror. This is to say that there is no objective reality, but that we can all “construct” our personal “discourses”⁵ about objects and their meaning⁶.

Extending this concept to the whole field of human disciplines, we arrive at the generic conclusion that there is no objective reality, but rather a set of different “realities” that depend on who performs the interpretative act and the context in which it takes place. In our case, we can say that the interaction between heritage and the person who benefits from it, thus determines its meaning.

The major risk that such a worldview implies is to consider the meaning of each cultural testimony as “meaningless”; on the other hand, it is a concept that allows us to eliminate the distance between the subject and the object, as it recognises the active role that culture plays in our lives. The post-structuralist attitude towards knowledge allows us to reinterpret the nature of heritage and our relationship to it. Furthermore, by bridging the gap between the individual and society, it gives us an understanding of individuals who are simultaneously moulded by society and by “social norms”, but whose actions also partly shape these structures. Let’s now see how – and if – this post-colonial perspective has been embedded in European cultural policies in the last 60 years.

Cultural policies in Europe: a bird’s eye view

Policy models

Although the role of culture in society and the relationship between art and ideology has undergone major changes over the centuries, culture still is a powerful factor in creating barriers, defining borders, legitimising the exclusion of marginalised groups, and reproducing inequalities.

Among the Enlightenment’s greatest emancipatory innovations is the idea of universal human rights: if art is the act of making and sharing meaning, and thus defining the human experience, then, self-evidently, it is, or should be, available to everyone. Its inclusion in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) made it also a political claim: Article 27 affirms that “everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits”⁷.

⁵ In post-structuralist theory, language is not considered as an impersonal system, but rather as connected to other systems and, in particular, to subjective processes. This conception of language is summarised in the concept of “discourse”.

⁶ Beginning with the distinction made by Saussure between meaning and signifier, Barthes goes further by questioning the existence of a true and indisputable element (the meaning), instead introducing the idea of a continuous flow of meanings that are generated by a third element, the interpreter/observer. Simply put, the meaning of the signifier changes depending on the person that interprets it.

⁷ See Art. 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948: “Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits”, https://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf.

The right to participate in the cultural life of the community should be seen – to say it with Matarasso – “as a safeguard for the rights that precede it. Denying people the right to participate in the cultural life of the community is to deny them a voice. And preventing people from being heard is the first step to denying them other rights”⁸.

Cultural policies in Europe take inspiration from international documents such as the already mentioned Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Art. 27, and the Faro Convention, which underlines the role of communities in shaping the values of heritage, in a vision of heritage and its connected values as a process and not as something fixed and immutable; on the other hand, data on cultural participation show that a quite low percentage of European citizens participate in cultural activities and, far more important, this percentage is made by homogeneous groups of people in terms of social, cultural and economic background⁹.

Research of the Council of Europe shows that participation in cultural activities is related to aspects of inclusive societies in Europe¹⁰. Cultural participation more generally and specific forms of cultural activity, especially artistic expression, online creativity, and passive participation, are indeed strongly associated with trust, tolerance and related dimensions of an inclusive society. The analysis has also revealed that stronger cultural industries and – to the extent measured – a more solid cultural infrastructure coincide with higher levels of cultural participation and could therefore provide clues regarding where policies or initiatives might contribute indirectly to improving social cohesion.

But which are the main barriers to cultural participation (Fig. 3) and how could they be overcome? Barriers can be geographical, physical, economic, and cultural and in Europe many attempts have been made in the last 60 years to tackle them.

Fig. 3: Main reasons for not participating in cultural activities (source: EUROSTAT, Cultural Statistics, 2019)

The lack of interest can be connected to the lack of perceived relevance, which can, in turn, be considered as a consequence and as a cultural barrier due to lack of knowledge, of habit and

⁸ F. Matarasso, *A Restless Art. How participation won and why it matters*, Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation, Lisbon and London 2019, p. 44.

⁹ EUROSTAT, *Cultural Statistics*, 2019, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3217494/10177894/KS-01-19-712-EN-N.pdf/915f828b-daae-1cca-ba54-a87e90d6b68b?t=1571393532000>

¹⁰ Council of Europe, *Cultural Participation and Inclusive Societies*, 2017.

of self-confidence related to feelings like inadequacy, distance, inappropriateness. Education still has a significant impact on cultural participation: in 10 Member States, more than 90% of people with high (tertiary) educational attainment attended cultural activities. Cultural participation of people analysed in relation to their income shows a similar pattern to that observed when looking at educational attainment: the higher the income level, the higher the participation.

These barriers are strictly related to issues such as access, participation and representation (see chapter "Policy models"), converging in the definition of Audience Development (AD) as a strategic and dynamic process enabling cultural organisations to place audiences – understood not only as visitors, but also as individuals and communities – at the centre of their strategy and activities.

In order for this to happen there are key issues we need to address, such as the legitimacy of public support for the arts and the creation of a cultural democratic space; the development of access (not only to cultural consumption, but also to the means of artistic production and distribution), participation and cultural diversity; the overturning of alienation processes and the development of pluralist and democratic values; the correlation between cultural and social capital; the connection between identity, culture and positive freedom; a notion of culture not only as a specific policy domain, but also (and foremost) as a transversal and horizontal factor of social and cultural regeneration.

Elite culture, as opposed to popular culture, is traditionally considered the expression of the ruling class, determining who is entitled to take part in the above mentioned processes, and who is not: if we consider museums for example, it's safe to assume that in many respects they represent an "institutionalised" form of exclusion, as they are products of the establishment and authenticate the established or official values and image of a society in several ways, directly, by promoting and affirming the dominant values, and indirectly, by subordinating or rejecting alternative values.

This discriminatory role of culture appears to have been significantly reduced in contemporary society as opposed to the past. In fact, on the one side it is no longer possible to consider the relationship between art and ideology as linear; on the other, it is extremely difficult today to define an ideology as the product of a monolithic, homogeneous ruling class, overlooking the complex nature of contemporary social stratification. The birth of cultural studies in the 1960s and the resulting development of the concept of subculture have subverted all social affiliations, drawing distinctions no longer based on the traditional criteria of social inclusion and exclusion. In contemporary societies, the specific worldviews of social actors are determined by class affiliation as much as by gender, ethnic and generational affiliation.

As for the notion of ruling class, the idea of cultural borders, meaning partitions socially created and recreated through negotiation processes between social groups, aimed at legitimising areas of discrimination and unequal distribution of resources, has become far more significant in contemporary society. The distinction between popular culture and elite

culture falls within this context, and is an expression of the inequality produced in the domains of artistic production and consumption.

There are three fundamental ways in which CH (and culture in broader terms) acts as an agent of social exclusion: access, representation, and participation (converging in the definition of audience development as a strategic and dynamic process placing audiences – understood not only as visitors, but also as individuals and communities – at the centre of cultural policies/actions). Addressing these three dimensions implies the transformation of cultural spaces into “safe” places – in the sense not of safe places because there it is possible to avoid confrontation, but on the contrary because they are places where to practise it safely, giving voice to all points of view¹¹.

1. The problem of access is a crucial one, since it is not only related to physical access (addressed and generally overcome in many spheres of social life thanks to regulatory measures and an increased awareness of the needs of disadvantaged people) but, and probably in a less visible way, to cultural access.
2. The issue of representation is crucial: if we consider, as an example, institutions such as museums and opera houses, they are the product of a “Eurocentric” conception of the world, and represent the dominant values of the learned European society of the XVIII and XIX century, as well as of the cultural policies of individual nation states. Quite clearly, in most cases they do not reflect the current values of our multi-cultural world and are perceived as exclusive institutions.
3. The lack of participation in the creative and decision-making processes is the third element which can generate exclusion within the cultural system of a society. The smaller the number of individuals (or social groups) playing an active role in such processes as well as in the safeguard, valorisation and enjoyment of CH, the greater the rift opening between the latter and citizens. The consequences of this divide are, on the one hand, the loss of awareness and sense of belonging on the part of individuals; on the other, the opportunity we miss in terms of the mutual knowledge and recognition which could stem from a genuine interaction and exchange between the different cultural expressions of our increasingly plural society.

¹¹ M. Vlachou, “Dividing issues and mission-driven activism”, in R.R. James e R. Sandell (eds.) *Museum Activism*, London, Routledge 2019, pp.47-57.

In the post-war era, European cultural policy makers have tried to address and solve these issues through different paradigms/approaches (Fig. 4):

Fig. 4: European policy models (source: elaboration of the authors after Lluís Bonet, Emmanuel Negrier (eds.), *Breaking the Fourth Wall: Proactive Audiences in the Performing Arts*, Kunnskapsverket, Elverum, report 5/2018)

The “excellence” model

This is the starting point of the other models, since it is the one stemming from the idea of a dominant élite which hands down culture to other members of society following a vertical path of transmission of knowledge. In this case, participation appears in its most limited forms. The model is still currently applied.

The “access development” model

Widely adopted in Europe during the 1950s and 1960s, this model was rooted in the welfarist idea of the democratisation of culture. Its aim was to extend access to a culture universally recognised as valid by identifying underrepresented groups, developing activities/programmes specifically designed to promote their participation, and removing barriers – whether they be physical, intellectual, cultural or financial. Today, access development in many European countries is embedded into the work of almost every publicly -funded arts and cultural organisation, and the principle that with public funding comes at least some obligation to extend the audience is generally accepted. One of the main weaknesses of the audience development model lies its unidirectional nature and missionary impulse.

The “socio-economic development” model

The second policy approach to securing legitimacy for public cultural investment consists in the “instrumental” use of cultural activities to further socio-economic goals. In this model, cultural and social actors identify specific situations of social malaise (such as urban deprivation, high rates of crime, early school-leaving, unemployment, racism and other forms of discrimination) and develop ad hoc programmes to solve them. The most eye-catching example of the socioeconomic development model is the use of culture and the arts in urban regeneration processes. But there is also a wide range of people-centred work with social objectives, such as the development of self-esteem and specific skills in individuals, or the promotion of self-determination in communities.

However, there are also dangers in the use of the arts for non-artistic objectives. In the case of urban regeneration schemes, for example, the excessive emphasis on short-term environmental and economic impacts at the expense of social and cultural ones (understanding the “impact on the culture of a place or community” as an impact on life-styles, identity, and the so-called “cultural governance”, i.e. citizenship, participation, representation, diversity), or unrealistically high financial or social expectations. In the case of community development programmes, the mediocrity of the resulting work from an artistic point of view, the sporadic nature of initiatives (failing to leave a permanent trace on the territory or community life), and a top-down approach, which is rarely based on a thorough analysis of participants’ needs and expectations.

Last but not least, this model is not at all taking into account the contemporary debate about forms of society and economy which aims at the well-being of all and sustains the natural basis of life (“degrowth”). It is still very much based on the current economic and social paradigm “faster, higher, further”, based on continuous competition which generates exclusion.

The “cultural inclusion (or democracy)” model

The third response to the democratic questions of public arts patronage – officially born with the term “cultural democracy” during the intergovernmental Conference of European ministers of culture promoted by UNESCO in Helsinki in 1972 – is based on the assumption that the role of cultural policies is to extend access not just to cultural consumption – as do the two approaches already mentioned – but to enlarge the franchise in terms of the means of artistic production and distribution. The emphasis is placed on the engagement of individuals not only as “audience”, but as actors and creators of culture, conceived as a form of expression promoting creativity and a positive sense of identity¹².

At the heart of this model is the acknowledgement that in order to genuinely combat social inequality and isolation, cultural institutions must become themselves more inclusive, through human resources development, new criteria for the allocation of funds, the experimentation

¹² At the time, in the global south, post-colonial thinkers like Freire were rejecting the subordination of their cultural authority. In Europe, elite culture was subjected to parallel critique by sociologists, including Pierre Bourdieu (F. Matarasso, *op. cit.*, p. 73).

of new partnership models, the inclusion of new skills, voices and narratives. In a word, our final destination: the creation of relationship zones. One of the greatest challenges is posed by the growing diversity of Western societies, requesting many cultural institutions to radically review the prejudice and assumptions which have traditionally underpinned not only their “culture” and programming, but also their organisational structure. In fact, an overview of cultural policies developed at both national and local level to promote social inclusion in Europe shows how crucial the issues of diversity and cultural dialogue have become, following the increase in migration flows not only in post-colonial countries, but also in those which turned from countries of emigration to the main European “magnets” of immigration.

Matarasso defines cultural democracy as “the right and capability to participate fully, freely and equally in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and create, publish and distribute artistic work. This definition adds to Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in three ways. First, it recognises that the right of participation in cultural life cannot be exercised without capability. Citizens who do not have access to knowledge, training, space, time and resources to participate in art are effectively denied the right to do so. The playing field is equal only when steps are taken to make it so for all. Secondly, it recognises that participation in the cultural life of the community includes acting as an artist. It is the difference between hearing and being heard, between being ‘passive receivers of culture’ and its active creators. Thirdly, it adds the qualifier ‘fully, freely and equally’ as a crucial reminder of the standard to which democracy aspires and the principle of universal human rights”¹³.

The model of cultural democracy - based on people’s legitimisation - is the only one which could as well encompass questions about cultural activism, gender issues and whose narratives we are talking about. In a word, is the only one which can step out the institutional dimensions, dealing with the grass roots, the independent, non-institutional or governmental voices.

Furthermore, it is also the only one which opens up to wider perspectives, in which the different dimensions of sustainability - social, economic, cultural and environmental - can be kept together. The policy approaches we have just described are not mutually exclusive, but create a democratic cultural space where they may be creatively combined, on condition they meet two fundamental conditions:

- that individuals and groups – especially those clearly “disadvantaged” – are not stigmatised as a “problem”, but are genuinely recognised as “resources”;
- that these policies are no longer perceived as a “foreign body”, but built right into the institutional fabric, and become an integral part of the thinking and practice of cultural policy makers and operators.

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 77.

If, however, these conditions are not met, we will keep addressing social and cultural exclusion issues only in response to specific situations, and this lack of an integrated and systemic vision will only compromise the impact of any of these policy approaches.

The role of the European Union

While policy in this area is primarily the responsibility of Member States, regional and local authorities, the EU is committed to safeguarding and enhancing Europe's CH through a number of policies and programmes.

Since its very first steps in 1974, the action of the then-called European Community (EC) in the cultural field has been closely related to the promotion of European identity and values. The emergence of actions in favour of culture was explicitly determined by the economic crises of the 70ies, which was undermining the process of European integration: the vague concept of European heritage as a core value to humanise the European project, going beyond merely commercial agreements among States, remained as the backbone of the emerging European cultural policy. The safeguarding of cultural diversity was already presented as part of the promotion of European heritage. However, its meaning and definition changed over time: until the 90ies, it mainly referred to diversity of national cultures within a European cultural unity; in the last decades, diversity has been placed at the core of the European Union (EU) cultural policy¹⁴.

In May 2008, it sent out a message full of profound reflections and guidelines to build democratic, equitable and sustainable societies, by valorising the diversity underpinning them, today more than ever. This message is at the core of the White Paper on Intercultural Dialogue "Living together as equals in dignity"¹⁵. In the foreword ("Dialogue – A Key to Europe's Future"), managing Europe's increasing cultural diversity – rooted in the history of our continent and enhanced by globalisation – in a democratic manner is recognised as a priority. The questions and issues at stake are complex and challenging; they imply a vision of the future, before we even start to devise operational strategies on how to respond to diversity. What is our vision of the society of the future? Is it a society of segregated communities, marked at best by the coexistence of majorities and minorities with differentiated rights and responsibilities, loosely bound together by mutual ignorance and stereotypes? Or is it a vibrant and open society without discrimination, benefiting us all, marked by the inclusion of all residents in full respect of their human rights? How can we valorise diversity, while at the same time preserving social cohesion?

¹⁴ The change of pace towards a decentralised use and approach to heritage is recognisable in Article 3.3 of the Lisbon Treaty (2000), which states: "The Union shall respect its rich cultural and linguistic diversity, and [...] ensure that Europe's cultural heritage is safeguarded and enhanced". The EU's role is, therefore, to assist and complement the actions of the Member States in preserving and promoting Europe's CH. The Commission has developed specific actions and a number of relevant policies and programmes, and also supports and promotes policy collaboration between Member States and heritage stakeholders. The acknowledgement of CH as a tool to promote diversity clearly visible in the latest EU policy document, an important role has been played by the CoE.

¹⁵ https://www.coe.int/t/dg4/intercultural/source/white%20paper_final_revised_en.pdf

The White Paper provides the vision; in fact, it believes that respect for, and promotion of, cultural diversity ... are essential conditions for the development of societies based on solidarity, ... that our common future depends on our ability to safeguard and develop human rights, as enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights, democracy and the rule of law and to promote mutual understanding. The proposed strategy is the intercultural approach, which offers a forward-looking model for managing cultural diversity. It proposes a conception based on individual human dignity (embracing our common humanity and common destiny). If there is a European identity to be realised, it will be based on shared fundamental values, respect for common heritage and cultural diversity as well as respect for the equal dignity of every individual. Intercultural dialogue allows us to prevent ethnic, religious, linguistic and cultural divides. It enables us to move forward together, to deal with our different identities constructively and democratically on the basis of shared universal values.

However, intercultural dialogue can only thrive if certain preconditions are met. The White Paper provides some guidance so as to advance it: the democratic governance of cultural diversity should be adapted in many aspects; democratic citizenship and participation should be strengthened; intercultural competences should be taught and learned; spaces for intercultural dialogue should be created and widened; and intercultural dialogue should be taken to the international level. The White Paper therefore tries to provide a conceptual framework, guidance and answers to decision makers and experts (institutions, local communities, civil society, religious/migrant organisations – who will have to address the democratic governance of cultural diversity in the near future), by identifying “Living together as equals in dignity” both as a goal and as a strategy.

In 2018 the EU launched the European Year of Cultural Heritage, whose aim was to encourage more people to discover and engage with Europe’s CH, and to reinforce a sense of belonging to a common European space. As the European Year of Cultural Heritage Report says, Europe’s CH “constitutes a shared source of remembrance, understanding, identity, dialogue, cohesion and creativity for Europe”¹⁶.

In May 2018, the European Commission presented a series of new initiatives in the fields of education and culture, including a proposal for ‘A New European Agenda for Culture’¹⁷. This Agenda outlines how the European Commission will support EU Member States in tapping into culture’s potential to foster innovation, economic growth and jobs as well as fostering ties between communities and strengthening Europe’s external relations. Most importantly, the New Agenda outlines how to build on the European Year of Cultural Heritage 2018 and sustain its legacy.

¹⁶ https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf.

https://europa.eu/cultural-heritage/european-year-cultural-heritage_en.html

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/culture/sites/culture/files/commission_communication_a_new_european_agenda_for_culture_2018.pdf

The New European Agenda for Culture has three strategic objectives:

- social dimension: harnessing the power of culture and cultural diversity for social cohesion and well-being;
- economic dimension: supporting culture-based creativity in education and innovation, and for jobs and growth;
- external dimension: strengthening international cultural relations.

Cultural heritage is a cross-cutting element in reaching these three objectives: namely the protection and promotion of “Europe’s cultural heritage as a shared resource, raising awareness of our common history and values and reinforcing a sense of common European identity”, but also the important need to “promote the skills needed by cultural and creative sectors, including digital, entrepreneurial, traditional and specialised skills”.

In 2020 the EU launched the [New European Bauhaus](#) (NEB), an initiative which , connects the [European Green Deal](#) to our living spaces and experiences and expresses the EU’s ambition of creating beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive places, products and ways of living. It promotes new ways of living where sustainability matches style, thus accelerating the green transition in various sectors of our economy and in our societies as well as other areas of our daily life. The aim is to provide all citizens with access to goods that are circular and less carbon-intensive, that support the regeneration of nature and protect biodiversity. The NEB initiative calls on all of us to imagine and build together a sustainable and inclusive future that is beautiful for our eyes, minds, and souls. The New European Bauhaus looks at projects, places, practices, and experiences that are:

- **beautiful**: aesthetically pleasing, but also inspired by art and culture, responding to needs and improving quality of experience beyond functionality;
- **sustainable**: in harmony with nature, the environment, and our planet;
- **inclusive**: encouraging a dialogue across cultures, disciplines, genders and ages.

Within the EU, CH has been used in a political way, with strong legitimising functions, in a top-down process of “Europeanisation of Europe”: however, the concept of heritage has subsequently become a tool in the hands of different actors who decided to promote their own vision of Europe, defending local cultural expressions, social and economic interests against the homogenising effects of European integration. The current position of the EU about heritage is based on the acknowledgment that the CH of the EU is a rich and diverse mosaic of cultural and creative expressions, inheritance from previous generations of Europeans and legacy for those to come. CH enriches the individual lives of citizens, is a driving force for the cultural and creative sectors, and plays a role in creating and enhancing Europe’s social capital. It is also an important resource for economic growth, employment and social cohesion, offering the potential to revitalise urban and rural areas and promote sustainable tourism.

On the other hand, referring back to the cultural policy models, it can be said that the EU is still very much anchored to a model of socio-economic development and not yet fully into that of cultural democracy: it has come very late to the table with intercultural dialogue,

gender balance, environmental issues, too often speaking of the larger metropolitan cultural buildings and institutions. The sector comprises freelancers and small organisations, who on a daily basis push the boundaries of cultural practice and presentation, testing new approaches, outside of the scrutiny of the public institutions. These are often the drivers of policy, not always acknowledged as such at EU level.

Audience development?

In 2015, the DG EAC of the European Commission launched a tender to conduct a «Study on Audience Development. How to place audiences at the centre of cultural organisations», in order to better understand the concept from a theoretical point of view and to analyse some case studies from all over Europe¹⁸.

Starting from the European Commission definition of AD as a strategic and dynamic process enabling cultural organisations to place audiences (understood not only as visitors, but also as individuals and communities)– at the centre of their action, the Study identified a model with two main aims addressed to current audiences: widening already active audiences and deepening their experiences; and diversifying the present audience to new target audiences. Responding to this conceptual distinction, the Study renamed the three main audience categories using non-academic, intuitive, easy-to-understand and hopefully inspiring categories: Audience by Habit, Audience by Choice and Audience by Surprise. This categorisation aims to:

- shift the perspective from the kind of use that people make of cultural contents, to the complex of factors that determine their decision to participate;
- underline that every citizen can become "audience" in different ways;
- stress that, for cultural organisations, developing different audiences means developing different kinds of relationships.

In more detail, this is how the three audience categories have been defined:

- **Audience by habit.** People who usually attend and/or participate in cultural activities, whose barriers to access are relatively easy to overcome, and towards whom different strategies are possible, such as audience education to attract similar audiences not currently participating; and taste cultivation to increase and diversify content and attendance. "Habit" in this framework means that those audiences are familiar with the same idea of being an audience, therefore cultural experiences are not just something they are used to doing, but much more a part of their identity and self-perception.
- **Audience by choice.** People who are not used to participating for reasons of lifestyle, lack of opportunities or financial resources; those for whom participating is not a habit, or who rarely choose to attend a show or a concert, but don't have any particular social

¹⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, *Study on Audience Development. How to place audiences at the centre of cultural organisations*, 2017, <http://engageaudiences.eu/files/2017/04/Final-report-NC-01-16-644-EN-N.pdf>.

or cultural disadvantage. To engage them, different strategies are possible, such as extended marketing but also education and participatory approaches.

- **Audience by surprise.** People that are hard to reach/indifferent/hostile, who do not participate in any cultural activity for a complex range of reasons, related to social exclusion factors, education and accessibility. Their participation could hardly be possible without an intentional, long-term and targeted approach.

Considering the above-mentioned issues, it is clear that these categories might in some cases overlap, since the boundaries among them are not neat. These are in fact flexible categories, which should help organisations in better understanding their audiences not as self-explaining segmentations, but as tools to be used in relationship with the strategies of widening, deepening and diversifying audiences and with the key action fields.

Fig. 5: Re-framing Audience Development objectives within a strategy
(source: Study on Audience Development)

Fig. 5 shows how the main objectives of Audience Development fit in the proposed frame. According to this interpretation, widening, deepening and diversifying are reinterpreted and slightly overlapped:

- **widening** refers both to current audience, Audience by Habit (increasing the audience of the same kind as the one who is attending today), and that part of Audience by Choice who has different or lapsed cultural consumption (attracting audience);
- **deepening** refers to strategies addressed to current audiences, those who by habit already value cultural practice but who can be more engaged in the perspective of taste cultivation (deepening and diversifying their cultural consumptions);
- **diversifying** refers both to strategies addressed to Audience by Surprise and to those Audiences by choice that have no or little chance to participate in the arts.

In all three cases, AD implies a first step, called REACH, based on the contact established between cultural institutions/organisations or CH itself and the audiences; and a second one, the ENGAGE phase, which consists in the active engagement of audiences through different tools and activities (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Key action fields (source: Study on Audience Development)

There are many strategies and tools to pursue different audience goals, and they can be classified in many different ways. For the purpose of the present study, the working group has identified four key action areas that represent the main assets for Audience Development strategies (Fig. 6). Far from being rigid categories, these instruments are the prevailing action assets (in practice as in rhetoric terms) for developing audiences, although with huge crossover characteristics. All these categories seem particularly interesting when it comes to focus on the impacts on organisations.

- **place** refers to those projects and cultural organisations' strategies strongly relying on the "place factor", creating links and building relationships based on a physical or virtual site, (e.g. interventions on space design, brand identity, etc.) and aimed to foster ownership towards a cultural and physical space;
- **digital** refers to those projects and cultural organisations' strategies strongly relying on the "digital factor", as a key aspect to reach audiences and foster engagement;
- **capacity building** refers to those projects and cultural organisations' strategies strongly relying on the "people factor": the empowerment of the staff and the development of their skills, competences and leadership are a key factor of different experiences, recognising the need for change inside the organisation in order to alter audience behaviour;

- **active participation/co-creation** refers to those projects and cultural organisations' strategies strongly relying on the "participatory factor". These are also particularly interesting in terms of their impacts on the organisation.

These categories have been integrated with key action fields such as **programming** (offer innovation in terms of format, programming, language, theme, place), **organisational change** and its implications, **use of data, collaboration and partnership**, as shown in the table below.

AD STRATEGIES							
	Place (WHERE)	Co-creation (WHO and WHY)	Use of data	Partnership (WITH WHOM)	Capacity building	Programming	Organisational change
METHODOLOGIES	<p>Identification of the place (real or virtual)</p> <p>Invitation to get to know it / to express personal visions about it</p>	<p>Engagement (invitation to participate), since the beginning of the project, of the selected communities, directly or through intermediate bodies ("nothing for us without us")</p> <p>Clear explanation of the aim of the project / activity</p> <p>Clear explanation about the choice of the communities / intermediate bodies</p>	<p>Impact assessment (qualitative evaluation aiming at investigating the occurred changes at different levels)</p>	<p>Choice of institutions; associations; allies and mediators; artists (due to their role in triggering processes)</p>	<p>Training on intercultural dialogue and on participatory planning addressed to cultural and social professionals, mediators, artists</p>	<p>Development of a community product (artistic production, work of art, personal stories, etc.)</p>	<p>Stable relationship among intermediate bodies (institutions, associations, mediators), specific communities and artists, to ensure continuity</p> <p>Implementation of a process of change (at organisational and personal level)</p>

		<p>Participatory planning: implementation of activities to create together "contact spaces" for intercultural dialogue and cultural projects with counter-narratives, thus establishing multisectoral partnerships and alliances</p> <p>Reward (acknowledgement; ownership; legitimisation; financial reward)</p>					
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Table 1: AD strategies and methodologies for community engagement (source: elaboration of the authors)

THE POWER OF WORDS

The power of words

Language is essential to expressing and communicating identities and thus a crucial pivot between different individuals, communities, societies and nations. This also implies that careless handling of language can be hurtful, cause detrimental damage and become a threat to a cohesive, inclusive society rather than a means to build bridges.

When it comes to cultural heritage, which is in and of itself an expression of the identity of communities and a firm foundation on which to build societal connections, extra care for language is becoming ever more important - not only in museums or libraries but also in the digital realm, where cultural data collections are increasingly accessible as digital literacy is on the rise.

These factors converge in the metadata describing such collections, representing the heritage communities in which they are rooted. And here the cultural heritage (CH) sector has identified an issue that occurs in many collections: historical, outdated descriptions that once fitted into common societal narratives, but are no longer considered appropriate. Even more striking are silences: gaps, omissions or inaccuracies in metadata resulting in a lack of expressivity and challenging the findability and representativity of important and precious collections.

Problematic metadata

The way in which objects are described and categorised in cultural heritage collections is a fundamental frame that enables or impedes audiences to find and access, connect to, research, learn, use and enjoy cultural heritage. In this sense **words matter**, because they are the first gateway for cultural heritage professionals and documentalists to reconnect heritage with people and provide an interpretation of various objects, all with different provenances and specific biographies.

Dealing with how metadata are worded has become a pressing matter as the cultural heritage sector wants to move towards realising the impact of cultural experiences as outlined in the Culture 3.0 model¹⁹, where culture consumers become prosumers, contributing through active participation and co-creation. For this to happen, it is vital that expressions of historical injustices and divisions are not only rectified, but used as a leverage for generating awareness of, insights in and attention for the use of language in collection and object descriptions.

Managing heritage collections should therefore entail a close look at the language used to categorise and describe artefacts back when they entered the museum or archive, and pointing out occurrences of language that is outdated, biased or even offensive. It should also entail looking at the present and the future to ensure that descriptions of historic artefacts as well as new objects are meaningful, respectful and (self-)expressive for a contemporary society and citizens with diverse and multicultural backgrounds.

¹⁹ Sacco, P.L., G. Ferilli and G.T. Blessi (2013), Culture 3.0. Cultural participation as a source of new forms of economic and social value creation: A European perspective, Milan.

Collection and documentation practices reflect the cultural and societal norms and power structures of the various time periods during which they were compiled. As a result, they may contain terms that are 'ethically outmoded' and have become inappropriate in modern society.

An example of an outdated term that we find in historical documents is 'half-blood' to denote people of mixed descent. Nowadays, there is a clear understanding that this term is offensive when discussing people, although it is still acceptable when discussing for example animals or plants. A wide array of similar terms, once clear pointers towards specific societal groups and communities, are now recognised as expressions of denigration, division and separation, not only by those groups and communities themselves, but also by society at large.

A well-known example is that of the term 'Eskimo' referring to the diverse Indigenous peoples of Arctic and subArctic North America, Greenland and Northeastern Siberia. While commonly used for decades, recently it has become clear that the term was never used by those communities themselves. Moreover, it harbours a pejorative meaning to the community members and has largely passed out of current language practices. Other, lesser-known terms, to the contrary have not been in use in recent decades, but remain latent in collective memory because of their lasting presence in archival material. A derogatory designation such as "Turcos" was used for Algerian soldiers in World War I: a historical case of language abuse that despite its austerity has not devaluated in terms of offensiveness.

Dynamics of meaning

The abovementioned examples go to show that meanings and sensitivities in language are not fixed but prone to change in different times, societal contexts and ethical frameworks. They also show that, even inadvertently, language can express bias, confirm stereotypes, cause division and misrepresentation.

Through language, CHIs regulate what kind of information is available to whom. They are sites for the negotiation of power, democracy, citizenship and belonging. Access and exposure to cultural heritage play an important role in the construction of a cultural memory and national identity and opinions, highlighting some narratives while neglecting and excluding others. For minorities, such as immigrants and LGBTQ+ persons, archives and museums are often sites of exclusion²⁰.

Furthermore, by (re)using biased narratives, professional audiences, such as researchers, educators, curators and creative industries, risk further perpetuating societal inequalities: a matter all the more pressing with regards to CHIs, since by the very act of defining a (limited) scope, they often are the very sources of inequity and exclusion. With a view to the ever-more stringent need and demand of citizens for a more diverse and inclusive society with matching

²⁰ Curating Access to Audiovisual Heritage: Cultural Memory and Diversity in European Film Archives | Dagmar Brunow

cultural apparatus, increasing diversity in collection policies and polyvocality in collections has to be at the core of CHI's missions, if they want to stay relevant and fulfil their public mission.

Sectoral strategies

Lately, many museums and national and international cultural institutions have set up programmes to 'decolonise' their collections or to highlight and explain the biases inherently linked to catalogue entries and descriptions accumulated over time. Actions and initiatives have been developed around the world to investigate language as one of the sources of the problem. The Getty Institute, for instance, is deeply involved in producing guides for correctly cataloguing or re-cataloguing objects with contentious descriptions²¹, and expanding on digital projects to address and correct the biases, such as the Getty Research Portal launched in 2012²². Several American museums and archives, too, have issued statements about the harmful or offensive language in descriptions and bias in cataloguing²³.

European institutions are also addressing the issue, but shortages in staff and budget concerns connected to the Covid crisis hindered a targeted and efficient approach and the development of a pan-European strategy. One important initiative has been undertaken by the National Museum of World Cultures in The Netherlands: The publication "Words Matter. An Unfinished Guide to Word Choices in the Cultural Sector" contains a glossary to help understand CHI professionals why a word can be particularly sensitive to a person, suggesting alternatives to potentially harmful terms²⁴. This (online) publication and the methodology used in its compilation have been an important inspiration for the DE-BIAS consortium.

Another European counteraction to be noted, is the working group of Europeana aggregators that has the goal to investigate and identify harmful language in collections, to raise awareness about the meaning of certain words and to come up with recommendations for archives on how to approach misrepresentation and underrepresentation.

The DE-BIAS approach

Despite these ongoing initiatives, so far a systematic and AI-supported approach to detect derogatory and harmful terms in descriptive metadata has been lacking. This is precisely what DE-BIAS proposes: **to improve the inclusiveness and representativity of cultural heritage metadata by making existing bias visible, guiding users in understanding the original context of words and providing insights into how they are currently perceived.**

To achieve this goal, DE-BIAS (i) developed a **digital tool** based on a vocabulary co-created with marginalised communities that is able to individuate and target sensitive language (ii) **builds capacity** within CHIs and aggregators, among other with the present reading resource,

²¹ https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/cco_cdwa_for_museums.pdf

²² <https://stedelijkstudies.com/journal/biases-within-digital-repositories/>

²³ <https://cataloginglab.org/list-of-statements-on-bias-in-library-and-archives-description/>

²⁴ Words Matter - Publication accessed February 15, 2024.

<https://amsterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/en/about-wereldmuseum-amsterdam/words-matter-publication>

to support and facilitate them in their efforts to detect and address biased language in metadata to their collections.

To achieve its ambition, DE-BIAS has collaborated and co-created with members of the communities represented in collections harboured by partner institutions as well as community allies - e.g. researchers, cultural professionals, educators and civil society representatives. Community members played a key role in shaping and populating a vocabulary to be used as a touchstone for potentially harmful use of language in descriptions of heritage objects, allowing content owners or aggregators to ensure that metadata represent community identities and backgrounds in a fair and respectful manner.

ENGAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES

Engagement methodologies

Meeting with empathy, circulating meanings

The reflection on the relationship spaces in which it is easier to meet, exchange ideas, and confront each other, opens up reflections that lead to questioning how each of us fits within this ideal relationship space. As the anthropologist Ulf Hannerz states²⁵, the idea of an organic relationship between a population, a territory, a unified political organism is one of those organised packages of meanings and significant forms that we are used to calling cultures.

Hannerz's starting point is that cultures are not themselves living creatures; they are shaped and conveyed by people in social and changing constellations, which pursue different aims. Starting from this approach to the complexity of the cultural process, it identifies four organisational frames that enclose different trends on how meanings are produced and circulate in social relations:

1. the first is life forms, to which everyone contributes with their daily lives. Interacting, observing us, listening to us, we take part in the cultural flow of the life form frame – not only the frame of the relationships of great personal intimacy but also the relationships of mixing, of strangers;
2. the second frame of cultural organisation is the State, here as a flow of meaning between the apparatuses and individuals as subjects / citizens. This coincides with all organised forms and institutions (schools, museums, theatres, media, civic rituals);
3. the third is represented by the market and contains transactional culture, that which links the buyer and the seller;
4. the fourth frame of reference is movement, which includes a highly deliberate management of meaning and the relationships between those involved.

This configuration brings out those who are potentially the actors involved in the management of meanings and significant forms, some with symmetrical relationships, others asymmetric and that also generate spatial and temporal implications.

Depending on the patterns of inclusion and social exclusion that influence interactions and attention structures, individual cultural repertoires may include different degrees of adaptation and familiarity with various parts of the entire cultural inventory, distributed along a continuum.

Another element that we must consider is that the encounter between different cultures creates what is called culture shock. Culture shock is that feeling of anxiety that can derive from the loss of most of the signs, symbols, codes that we consider familiar in social relationships in which we are involved or in the places where we live. They are the ways, the signs, the habits through which we orient our behaviour, and relate to each other. These signals (words, gestures, facial expressions, tone of voice, habits, norms, postures) are

²⁵ This chapter is largely taken from M.F. Guida, "Collective intelligence: thoughts in movement" in C. Da Milano, E. Falchetti, M.F. Guida (eds), *op. cit.*, pp. 193-201.

acquired in the growth stages and are part of everyone's culture. Balance and security depend on these factors.

Our brain is used to working following models/patterns that it recognises. Everything that does not fit into these models creates a cognitive dissonance that the individual tries to eliminate to reduce discomfort and activates a series of elaborating processes to compensate for the dissonance (for example, when trying to modify the cognitive world, or rather the world of cognitive representations that act internally, through knowledge, relationship, contact).

In this process, cultural organisations play a fundamental role. For migrants, public spaces and cultural spaces represent places of aggregation, of conviviality, of community life. These are opportunities, thanks to the mutual contribution of others, to counter the effects of culture shock through encounter, narration, and the sharing of time and interests.

Open dialogue

The metaphor of the meeting is a trace of an intra-cultural methodology of open dialogue. Openness to plurality is the first step towards a relationship with the other that is always the fruit of an experience, passing from assuming awareness of one's own contingency. Contingency which means "that we touch (tangere) our limits and the unlimited touches us (cum-tangere) tangentially". Knowing how to open up to this contingency, letting ourselves be touched by the other is what Panikkar calls knowing how to grasp the world's pluriversity.

In his book "Interreligious dialogue" he analyses the rhetoric of dialogue with four dialogical attitudes (exclusivism, inclusiveness, parallelism, interpenetration) that he uses to read inter-religious dialogue, but which potentially offers interesting ideas for reading dialogue in general.

Exclusivism contemplates a single vision, inclusivism a single vision that embraces everything; parallelism recognises a unique finality, whatever the specific itineraries, they run parallel to meet each other. Interpenetration offers us the possibility of considering our culture among the many, assuming this position, we approach our neighbour with interest and begin to discover how the other is involved in each of us and vice versa. Furthermore, Panikkar describes four models (geographical, physical, geometric, anthropological) which form a synthetic and extremely lively picture of the reality of dialogue and at the same time provide working tools for a real pedagogy of dialogue that must take into account the different meanings.

When we relate to others, different habitats of meaning emerge, which can expand and contract, and can identify with individuals or the community. In global ecumenism, multiple habitats of meaning can be shared. However, our habitats of meaning do not depend only on where we are physically exposed, but also on our ability to confront ourselves with it, the languages we understand, write or speak, our levels of literacy in relation to other symbolic forms, and so on.

Writing, for example, leads to identification with one language or another. In fact, for some time language has dominated cultural boundaries, since it coincided with the concept of Nation, while active involvement in other symbolic modes (art, music, gestures, body) has tended to be confined to local areas.

When people circulate and relate to their own meanings, and when meanings find ways to circulate even without people, territories cannot really be containers of cultures; the space of relationship is extended beyond the territorial boundaries and in this new space finds a new field of action of sharing, of diversity of experiences, of biographies, of looks, of voices among the different members of the community themselves.

Gramsci refers to communities as social strata, understood as individual nuances that, together with their cultural differences, challenge a homogeneous centre and that broaden the horizons of possibility, interpretation, and relationship²⁶.

However, the desire to deal with the Other and the concern to gain skills in cultures that are initially foreign, calls into question psychological, social, cultural aspects that question how we place ourselves in space, where cultures meet, engage with each other, coexist. Relational competence with different cultures brings a sense of mastery as an aspect of the Self: personal understanding expands and allows you to relate to others, to create new images of the world.

The Indian anthropologist Appadurai identifies different landscapes (scape) that represent contemporaneity and within which communities move. He calls these ethno-scapes, the panorama of people in movement (tourists, migrants, refugees, nomads etc...) who open the way for new relationships and new cultural landscapes²⁷.

In this new landscape, cultural processes are not always populated by prosocial attitudes but are often generators of conflict. Society – according to Dewey – is the result of the relationships of individuals with each other and all relationships are interactions, not fixed modules. The interactions that make up a human society are the give and take of participation, a sharing that increases, that expands and deepens the capacity and meaning of the interacting factors that favour democratic participation²⁸.

The democratic participation mentioned by Dewey strongly emphasises the intimately social and "participant" nature of the individual, the individual habit of expressing oneself and empathising. In general terms, empathy includes all those processes for which the individual employs the way the brain understands the world to understand the internal states of the other: identification, emotional contagion, cognitive empathy.

Empathic processes

Empathy is made up of an emotional dimension and a cognitive dimension. The first consists of an emotional response oriented towards the other and congruent with the perception of its

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.*

well-being. The second coincides with the assumption of perspective or role and consists in the capacity of a person to represent the mental state of the other, at the cognitive level, to deeply understand the inner experience and the point of view without necessarily being emotionally involved.

The effects of the activation of empathic processes can improve intergroup relations and intervene profitably in reducing prejudice. In particular, the assumption of perspective is an effective strategy to free social thought from prejudice to favour cultural collisions and cultural encounters. Socio-cultural and cognitive aspects are fundamental for orientation in life; the cultural gap widens with the failure of the social networks that make someone feel recognised as part of a community. The lack of relational structures leads to the inability to manage uncertainties.

In the new life experience, the secure networks of relationships disintegrate, human relationships become fragmented and discontinuous and replace the networks of permanent reciprocity. The protective nets, woven and protected by their own means, once made available by neighbourly relations or family relationships, where they could find refuge, have in any case suffered a considerable weakening in the new country. The new life experience in which we find ourselves is characterised by what are called weak ties, which have the characteristic of changing often and being timed.

Relationships imply a constant effort to reach a certain degree of depth, continuity, recognition, sharing of life experiences. There are different ways to nourish relationships, to foster the search for meaning through value and spiritual tools, where solidarity is one of the fundamental aspects that gives access to participation, cultural life and relationships. A certain clarification to acquire elements of interpretation in reading the relationships is that it is necessary to consider that they are nourished in a time and a space: two conceptual categories that presuppose a field of interaction – a social space to be built and in which to interact – and a time of sharing.

The time variable often represents a limit to the development of relationships: a person rooted in one culture comes into contact with another, with its practices and its meanings in a temporary manner. If we think of the activities of involvement of migrants in the cultural life that some cultural institutions carry out, we know that often sporadic occasions remain that do not develop over time.

Asymmetry and heterogeneity

If we were to draw the cultural flow of the contemporary world, we would realise how asymmetrical it is; it is stronger from the centre to the periphery, temporary, occasional and linked to thrusts that do not fit into long-term relational strategies where relationships live, grow and develop.

It is essential to promote social spaces as inclusive and heterogeneous; as a relational, cultural expression; as multipliers of relationships that extend contacts with other cultures. The so-called participatory goods that give rise to the intimate and everyday sphere reach

multiple areas of social action, highlight the bond and the connection, and produce social value by uniting a person with networks and groups to which they belong. The role of the cultural sector in this is fundamental, as a useful resource for social cohesion, as a place for sharing, meeting, and reflecting on plurality.

It is essential to work on expanding opportunities for socialisation and on improving opportunities for participation to encourage expanded involvement without limits and boundaries. The need for cultural communities as spaces of shared expression, of social interaction, of collective encounter, places emphasis on concrete opportunities for socialisation, on the creation of contact areas in which relationships can be nourished.

Some city designers recognise the need to consider the métissage that is created in public spaces: museums, theatres, libraries, schools have always been the backbone of the culture of cities. Today they are called to respond to new social needs, to dialogue with everything that happens outside and to have an openness towards others in order to create connective structures that can facilitate relationships and knowledge, to create what is called “urban pedagogy”. Cities can also provide energy and opportunities for training, the need to feel welcomed by someone and somewhere, to belong, to participate in ritual repertoires. The opportunity at an interpersonal level to put into play the visions of the world, in relation to cultures constituted by a set of emotions, needs, memories, encounters, feelings, existences, readings, abilities, learning modalities, knowledge.

Fig. 7: Community engagement and intercultural dialogue (source: elaboration of the authors)

Methodological focus on storytelling

Storytelling (ST) is strictly related to many of the above-mentioned categories (and to AD in general):

- place: the process of ST normally starts in a physical or virtual place related to the experience that the storytellers will talk about;
- capacity building: it is related to the need of training of facilitators, stakeholders and storytellers in the principles and use of ST and in its understanding as a means to engage audiences (in the case of MEMEX, the training phase will address the partners implementing the pilot projects and their stakeholders, as well as the storytellers);
- co-creation: the process of storytelling implies that storytellers are the owners of their stories. This means that the level of co-creation embedded in the final result (the story) is very high and strictly related to the level of engagement of the storytellers;
- use of data: ST can be used as a very effective and powerful means of qualitative evaluation, especially in terms of phenomenographic evaluation, which means measuring the changes which happened during the process;
- partnership: storytelling is a collective process which needs cooperation among different stakeholders in order to be effective (in the case of the MEMEX, strong partnerships will be established not only between technological and cultural partners, but also among partners, social and cultural stakeholders - intermediate bodies, cultural institutions, etc. - and participants).

But what is storytelling?

Definition and value proposition

Barthes affirms that "In this infinite variety of forms, (narrative) is present at all times, in all places, in all societies; indeed narrative starts with the very history of mankind; there is not, there has never been anywhere, any people without narrative; all classes, all human groups, have their stories, and very often those stories are enjoyed by men of different and even opposite cultural backgrounds: narrative remains largely unconcerned with good or bad literature. Like life itself, it is there, international, trans-historical, transcultural"²⁹.

Storytelling is a widespread communication practice, whose origins, motivations, and uses are rooted in the mental-cultural complexity of human beings. It is therefore of great interest for a variety of disciplines, both at a theoretical and at a practical level, aiming to understand how and why it became so pervasive, what are its mechanisms, what is its educational, social, or even therapeutic role. Storytelling usually consists in reporting on facts, events or actions carried out in a given time and space by human and non-human beings in the shape of

²⁹ R. Barthes, An introduction to the Structural Analysis of Narrative in «New Literary History», Vol. 6, No. 2, 1975, p. 237.

conversations, written texts, literary works, multi-media communication, movies, music, etcetera.

All human languages and cultural-communication codes include storytelling: fairy tales, for example, comprise narratives from all over the world. Storytelling is typical of both oral/informal and formal cultures, artistic expressions included. It therefore unfolds as a common expressive feature of all human beings, whose minds gather and interpret sensory information, events, and emotions, and organise them in the shape of a story.

Thinking caps

Today, the structure of the human mind is described with a systemic and complex approach. In his fundamental essay "Frames of mind" (1985), Howard Gardner describes human beings as endowed with at least nine relatively distinct faculties: logical-mathematical, linguistic, spatial, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal, naturalistic, and existential intelligences. These are present, albeit in different combinations, in all human beings, and interact with each other through complex mechanisms. For other scholars, human thought is based on three fundamental types of intelligence: analytical (the ability to break up, compare, examine, evaluate, question, research and explain causes), practical (the ability to use tools and create something concrete) and creative (based on intuition, imagination, discovery, the ability to produce something new, speculating, inventing). Among the different mental abilities, all human beings are endowed with narrative competencies and forms of thinking; other abilities arise in abstract or symbolic form (e.g., formal disciplines and languages). The different reasoning forms and competencies and the different languages are used in different ways and contexts. Narrative and symbolic thinking can support and enrich each other.

Abstract thinking is ideal to interpret what is regular, expected, normal, ordinary, not surprising, mundane: the things we give for granted. By contrast, the narrative thinking encapsulated in stories and storytelling is ideal to talk about the exceptional, the extraordinary, the unexpected, the unusual; all this gives rise to curiosity and the excitement we all feel when we listen to a good story. Stories, therefore, are valued by the mind and heart alike. They have the power to ascend from the universal to the particular, as opposed to the power of science to rise from the particular to the general.

The value of storytelling is also reiterated in the development of knowledge. Logical-scientific and narrative thinking are the fundamental ways in which all human beings organise their understanding of the world (Bruner, 1997). They take different forms in different cultures, but no culture exists without them. However, most schools consider narrative arts – songs, drama, novels, theatre etc. – as something which is more "decorative" than necessary, something to make our leisure time pleasant. But this doesn't mean that we don't construct our cultural roots and the beliefs we hold as the most important in the shape of a story; and what is so fascinating for us is not only the content of these stories, but the ability with which they are told. Even our immediate experience, what happened to us yesterday or the day before, is expressed in the shape of a story. Yet more significantly, we represent our lives (to

ourselves as well as to others) in the form of a tale: most probably, storytelling has the same importance for cultural cohesion as it has in structuring an individual's life.

All human beings, everywhere and in every time, have used storytelling. Informally, we tell stories virtually every moment of our daily lives. Even children soon learn the rhythm and structure of storytelling. Our mind is organised to perform this function. Individuals learn/gather information by observing the actions, behaviours and emotions of their fellow human beings through the "mirror neurons" system, which allows us to understand and anticipate the actions, movements and intentions of others. Narrative thinking can perceive and create connections between sequences of actions and feelings.

Stories as communication

Narrative thinking and storytelling may be understood as adjustments connected with the social needs of our species. Through these competencies, we can communicate actions, events, dangers, the need for remedial actions; we nurture social relationships; we share emotions; we teach; we exchange knowledge and information. From a social point of view, the narrative form is particularly appropriate because of its practical, immediate, and direct quality: it provides information on an acting subject or on the sequence of his/her actions, the times, and places. Moreover, the narrative structure is easily accessible also for those individuals who don't have a sound formal culture, while other expressive, explanatory and communication structures require practice and teaching.

The ability to formulate and create stories also has an adaptive value in its potential to explain what is mysterious or inexplicable through the available knowledge, thereby responding effectively to the human need for mysticism. Cultures in every place and time produced explicative models of reality in the shape of cosmogonies, legends, myths, and fantastic stories with universal symbols. This also explains why human beings value storytelling more than description or other expressive forms: description may support, integrate narration, but does not have the same cognitive and emotional role. At a more basic level, storytelling is cherished because it involves individuals, whether storytellers or listeners, in an empathic, rather than simply intellectual, relationship; because it refers to individual or social human experience, to aspects of life which all human beings can recognise and share almost "innately". Likewise, storytelling doesn't coerce individuals into a given language, and is open to multiple meanings and interpretations. Finally, storytelling encourages inspiration and creativity, thereby nurturing new ideas, stories, meanings, and cultural forms.

Paradigms for postmodern times

The complexity of contemporary environmental, social, cultural, and technological issues requires complex mental forms, new paradigms of thought and new approaches to education. The educational needs and the competencies needed to deal with complexity are identified in forms of systemic, complex, critical, and relational thinking. Complex and systemic thinking require narrative, rather than abstract and symbolic styles. Storytelling has a potential of and for understanding, dealing with complexity: it allows to connect information

and knowledge, perceptions and emotions, experiences, symbolic data, and visions of the world.

The different steps through which the storytelling experience leads storytellers and listeners can be summarised as such:

- contact;
- familiarity;
- diving;
- identification;
- emersion;
- distance;
- transformation.

Through storytelling, we exercise and reinforce mental abilities which are relational, unifying, transversal and related to a context; through storytelling, it is possible to offer to the narrator and listeners an experience of high co-communication and educational value: values, knowledge, experiences can be transmitted by putting in place the analytical thinking of a logical and rational type.

Today the time is ripe to talk about participatory culture with a view to sharing and co-creation processes, that gives visitors/participants an active role not only in the enjoyment but also in rereading CH in a different way. New technologies give the public a voice, but the starting point cannot be technology: storytelling must be upstream of the choice of technology that we decide to use.

Stories (imagined, told) have a great individual and social value. They play a fundamental role in language learning, in constructing and exchanging knowledge, in shaping education processes, in sharing moral and ethical rules, values and traditions. They contribute to shaping or reinforcing personal identity and self-esteem; all individuals, in fact, define and recognise themselves in a process of "narrative creation of the self", through both personal stories and stories about their families, communities and cultures of origin. The shaping of an individual identity also makes it possible to understand others and helps creating or consolidating social identities and shared cultures. In turn, these shared, community cultures enrich narrative thinking with their stories, traditions, languages, educational practices, thus building the symbolic, cognitive, and expressive features of the different peoples in different times and places.

Stories play a fundamental role also in the "creation", recognition and conservation of CH. Objects, places, events, traditions, customs, rites are valorised and transformed in "heritage" by the stories conceived by expert/cultured or popular/folk communities. CH lives for, is nurtured, and preserved by the stories that it narrates or by which it is narrated. Stories and narration inspire and constitute the "core" of all kinds of past and modern CH (e.g., in the visual arts as sculpture and painting, in the literary heritage as poetry and literature, in the music as ballads, symphonic poems, opera, in the theatre, dance and in the modern and contemporary arts as photography and filmmaking).

Educational practices in GLAMs

The post-modern and constructivist education emphasises the relevance of storytelling in the construction of thinking, learning, interpretation of reality and in formal and informal communication. Due to this epistemological pedagogical and social acceptance, storytelling gained a preferential place in the communication/presentation of the CH in museums. Scientific museums adopted narrative strategies of communication and mediation before other cultural institutions to promote cultural accessibility, because of the consciousness that storytelling facilitate understanding of exhibitions and engage more intensely visitors, as compared to explanatory or descriptive strategies. The assumptions of storytelling in museums are based alike on the paradigm of the power of narration in social communication, education and learning and in the intercultural dialogue and finally in the outlining individual and community identities. Storytelling in museums makes communication more accessible also to people less used to formal culture or representative of different cultures. Furthermore, storytelling engages people in an empathic and not only mind relationships; it encourages inspiration and creativity which in turn nurture new ideas, stories, meanings, and new cultural paths.

In post-modern museums, exhibitions tell stories about museums themselves, objects, specimens and their interpretive cultures, people, communities, places, territories, events, cultures, and formal disciplines. Texts are designed mainly in narrative framework; so, they are involving and interactive. Manifold forms of today's storytelling enrich museum communication (also by immersive and pluri-sensorial techniques) to reinforce the impact of exhibitions and educational experiences: pictures, comics, sound and music, theatre, and other performances. Narrative messages frequently reach visitors outside museums also by "narrative" buildings.

Many museums incite and collect stories created by visitors after their experiences and impressions (inclusive storytelling). Also, in several museums production of stories by the public has become an essential part of educational programs, such as intercultural ones; storytelling enhances involvement and adds value to visitors' cognitive and affective experiences. Moreover, it enriches museum culture by promoting new interpretations. In a participatory and universal accessibility perspective, storytelling plays a unique and unmatched role. Museums reveal to be invaluable laboratories for autobiographic, collective, intercultural, and transcultural stories. In museums, storytelling is memory (therefore belonging and identities) and imagination (therefore becoming future): storytelling is the bridge between past and future.

Blueprint of a storytelling workshop

The structure of a storytelling workshop³⁰ could follow the steps detailed below:

³⁰ The same structure can be applied to Digital Storytelling, even though in DS there are 2 more phases related to the recording of the storyteller's voice and to the editing of the images, videos, sounds, etc.

1. Informative session (**briefing**). A ST workshop usually begins with a briefing session; its aim is to inform participants in more detail about the activities in which they will be involved, to reassure them on the work scheduled for the following days.
 - a. Different typologies of stories should be illustrated in order to show to participants the final results of the process and the diverse range of stories it was possible to develop.
 - b. The second step of this phase is the direct contact with the object/topic of the future story (in case of CH, this might happen through a visit, a walk, participation in a performance, etc.); this step should be followed by a third step of sharing of the impressions/emotions/thoughts generated by the second step;
2. **Writing**. The choice of which story to tell starts with the “story-circle”. Through several games, the facilitator helps the storyteller to identify the topic for the story which will then be produced in digital format. Stories are about a change which took place inside the storyteller, the resolution of a conflict, a particular memory or a decision that changed the storyteller’s professional or personal life. The storytelling session starts by reassuring everyone that this was a safe environment, in which all participants could express themselves without fear of making a mistake. The rule is that what is told within the circle remains inside the circle. Through writing games, storytellers are encouraged, first, to try and identify stories in a creative way, drawing inspiration from their daily lives, secondly, to convey the experience behind the objects they had brought with them by sharing it with the group and, finally, to choose the story to tell. Once the story is identified, participants are allowed a short time to write their texts”. In this phase, participants are encouraged to share their stories between them, so as to make sure that they are meaningful or that the message they want to convey is clear;
3. **Sharing**. Sharing stories with the other participants is a moment of strong empathy, as well as an occasion to go over the significance of the whole process and to clear up possible doubts. The observations of participants can be also gathered through questionnaires at the beginning, during the workshops and at the end of the training course.

It is precisely because of the fundamental role played by the intimate and emotional part of personal stories, that the planning of a range of **icebreaker activities** at the beginning of the workshops is so important for team building and the creation of an environment perceived as open and safe enough for individuals to open themselves to others.

In this context, **the role of the facilitator is crucial** in order to create such an environment and to guide storytellers in identifying and developing a personal story which is particularly meaningful. A delicate task for the facilitator is to help storytellers sum up “the history of the moment” in a few words. Although it may seem inconsiderate to advise someone to omit parts of the story, being asked to use a limited number of words helps the creative process and urges the storyteller to focus on a single moment and to examine it in depth. The same

goes with the time limit characterising each one of the five phases: participants are invited to concentrate and to carry out whatever is required in that phase within a given time, often drawing from skills they didn't expect to have. Organising the workshop while respecting all phases and the related schedule allows one to understand and appreciate its dynamics with a view to adapting it to one's own professional context.

Good practices: community engagement projects³¹

In this section we listed some good practices implemented by ECCOM, with specific reference to digital storytelling as a tool for community engagement.

[DIAMOND – Dialoguing Museums for a new Cultural Democracy \(2012-2014\)](#)

Funded by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the EU, it was conceived with the aim of providing a research contribution to overcoming the cultural barriers that prevent the use of heritage by potentially excluded citizens. The project questioned the social role of museums and the strategies for involving non-traditional audiences and recognised the broad potential of digital storytelling to support the inclusive role of culture and museums, as well as a tool for assessing the social impact that the activities carried out in cultural institutions can have on citizens. Hence the choice of connecting scientific museums and research centres in Italy, Romania and Spain to experiment with digital storytelling as a narrative technique suitable for reaching traditionally marginalised and disadvantaged audiences. Museum and social mediators were involved in training courses that aim to bring the public closer to the use of new technologies for museum storytelling. DIAMOND also took the form of pilot projects in the various partner museums - Civic Museum of Zoology in Rome (Italy), "Grigore Antipa" National Museum of Natural History in Bucharest (Romania), "Ion Borcea" Museum of Natural Sciences in Bacau (Romania), Museum of Natural Sciences of Valencia (Spain) - aimed at groups of adults coming from different situations but who share characteristics of social marginality. The results of the project converged in a manual in 4 languages³² and became the theme of a Grundtvig training course aimed at 20 professionals in the museum/ social sector. The project was selected by the Lazio Region among the "2016 Good Cultural Practices" to be disseminated for the use of cultural resources.

[MUA – Welcoming museum \(2016-2018\)](#)

Promoted by the Department of Tourism and Cultural Industry of the Puglia Region through the Teatro Pubblico Pugliese, it involved the Biblio-Museum Poles of the provinces of Lecce and Brindisi in a training course to build innovative skills and practices to improve the accessibility to cultural heritage and to promote it among new citizens. Eighteen museums became community centres: an important basis for the creation of a territorial network to share and discuss the themes of intercultural and social sustainability. Aimed at museum

³¹ In this chapter are listed some good practices implemented by ECCOM, with specific reference to digital storytelling as a tool for community engagement (<https://www.youtube.com/user/eccomprogetti>).

³² C. Da Milano, E. Falchetti (eds.), *Stories for Museums, Museums for Stories*, Vetrani Editore, Nepi 2015.

operators, university students, agencies involved in reception and foreign communities residing in Puglia, MUA sought to develop skills to manage integration and dialogue between cultural and migrant institutions and aims to make cultural heritage a gateway to an active citizenship process. Digital storytelling was the tool chosen to multiply the narratives of heritages and museums and to involve new audiences: ECCOM carried out training meetings for operators, called upon to produce short videos to narrate museums in a plural way and from new perspectives. Two artist residences were carried out with artists who worked with the migrant communities of Lecce and Brindisi, experimenting with new creative and narrative methods and through the co-design of exhibitions.

[Art Clicks](#) - An intercultural training path for operators of Italian cultural institutions, focused on exploring the potential of culture in the relationship with diversity **(2018-2019)**

Within the project, funded by the Stavros Niarchos Foundation, 15 operators from Italian cultural institutions - such as museums, libraries and theatres - and 10 migrant and refugee artists and cultural operators worked together for a year in Rome, in a 200-hour training workshop on the theme of intercultural exchange and planning. This with the aim of strengthening and expanding intercultural skills and practices on the Italian territory where different ethnic groups and cultures meet. The project promoted the exchange and sharing of good practices, in order to improve the ability of places of culture to stimulate integration, support cultural participation of migrants and intercultural projects. Art Clicks embraced research and training and experiments with cultural activities in a multicultural context, directly and indirectly involving c. 20,000 people.

Playground: one of the pilot projects of Art Clicks

[DRIS](#) - Co-creating intercultural Societies: a Focus on Racism and Discrimination **(2020-2022)**

Funded by the European Union's 2014-2020 Creative Europe Programme, it emerged from the observation that different and effective initiatives, albeit isolated, exist but at an initial or pilot stage. The project aimed to enhance respect and mutual understanding for cultural diversity

through intercultural dialogue and to facilitate cultural participation of migrant communities, by developing effective counter-narratives through art and culture, especially among multi-ethnic and multicultural communities in three cities: Barcelona, Berlin and Rome. Discrimination continues to affect large numbers of new citizens, ethnic minorities, immigrants and their children, the fight against racism and xenophobia is still an on-going priority that deserves all our attention. The international community has indeed worked for the integration of migrants and refugees; however, these processes are often hindered by discrimination and violence that undermine positive attitudes and hamper meaningful participation in society. The project was underpinned by the Agenda 2030, since it directly addressed different Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), namely: Goal 4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all; Goal 5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls; Goal 11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. The project produced an "[Intercultural Dictionary](#)" in 5 languages.

[MEMEX \(2020-2022\)](#)

Funded by the Horizon2020 Programme of the EU, the MEMEX project promoted social cohesion through collaborative, heritage-related tools that provided inclusive access to tangible and intangible cultural heritage and, at the same time, facilitated encounters, discussions and interactions between communities at risk of social exclusion. These tools empowered communities of people with the possibility of welding together their fragmented experiences and memories into compelling and geolocalised storylines using new personalised digital content linked to the pre-existent European Cultural Heritage (CH). The tools of MEMEX allowed the communities to tell their stories and to claim their rights and equal participation in European society. To this end, MEMEX nurtured actions that contribute to, rather than undermine, practices of recognition of differences by giving voice to individuals for promoting cultural diversity.

[IMPROVISA – Life in motion \(2020-2022\)](#)

Funded by the Creative Europe programme, the project explored new ways of involving audiences, in particular young people and communities with difficulties in accessing cultural heritage and artistic content, through the use of audiovisual and new technologies and with the collaboration of artists, museums and experts in audience development. IMPROVISA sought to promote the international mobility of artists, called to experience residences in the three cities involved (Athens, Ljubljana, Lublin) and a creative Co-Lab for the development of artistic activities, to be implemented in 72 workshops for audiences in the three participating museums. The project also provided for intersectoral mobility, promotion, knowledge enhancement and exchange between artists, museum professionals, ICT specialists and audience development experts. Digital became a tool to explore and develop models of interaction and participatory artistic activities for the (re) interpretation of cultural heritage and the promotion of intercultural dialogue. In fact, in support of all activities, the IMPROVISA

Mobile App consists of an intuitive and creative tool to bring audiences closer to improvisation through audiovisual and artistic interaction.

More good practices: published methodologies³³

This annotated selection of good practices was compiled on the basis of DE-BIAS partners' suggestions.

[Sociocracy For All](#)

This nonprofit action helps organisations, communities, and collectives to learn how to organise themselves and take **equality and transparency-based** resolutions by adopting in their decision-making process elements taken from the concept of "sociocracy". Sociocracy is a governance system developed in the 1980ies which draws on the use of **consent**, rather than majority voting, in discussion and decision-making by people who have a shared goal or work process. These elements might be useful in the context of equality-based collaborative and co-creative tasks involving communities.

Interesting sociocracy-related methodologies include:

- the use of **rounds** in meetings to ensure equality and transparency;
- trusting that **group intelligence** has a bigger impact than individual intelligence;
- the use of **facilitation methods** from sociocracy to guide conversations in groups;
- adoption of a **feedback loop** to learn and assess actions' impact.

[LGBTQIA+ Tours](#)

The Victoria & Albert Museum (South Kensington, London) organises monthly tours -led by volunteers- aiming at unveiling hidden stories of diverse gender and sexual identities through the discovery of objects and collections displayed at the museum. The initiative focuses on audience engagement through learning via the collection's object & interaction with the volunteer guides.

[LGBTQ histories trail](#)

Object trails organised by the British Museum (London) based on LGBTQ histories. The audience can choose among two trajectories: a fifteen object trail and a three object trail - depending on how much time the audience can dedicate to the tour. The tours allow audience engagement through learning via the collection's objects as well as both a live and digital discovery of the museums' collections. In fact, the public can either choose to go through the chosen trail online and download the audio explanation or go directly for the live experience.

[Queering the Museum Project](#)

The project's main goal is to *"facilitate critical dialogues between community members and museum practitioners, addressing the role that museums play in forming social norms around gender and sexuality"*. Also, it intended to connect community members and museums and

³³ This annotated selection of good practices was compiled by Roberta Pireddu, KU Leuven, on the basis of consortium partners' suggestions.

facilitate their interaction and collaboration for the achievement of common goals. During its activity period, the project organised a series of workshops and initiatives focused on alternative & queer histories in the museums. Particular attention was given to the following approaches:

- facilitating critical dialogues between communities & museums addressing the role of museums in forming social norms around gender and sexuality;
- creating a connection between community members & organisations;
- allowing participants' stories to be shared in the project's blog.

Also, within the context of this project, a Digital Storytelling initiative, which aimed at encouraging workshops' participants to transform their stories into digital narratives, was launched. The audience was asked to use their own narration and photos to create a 3 to 4-minute video, which was then screened at a symposium.

[Traiettorie di sguardi: Narrating Bologna's museums and libraries from a decolonial perspective](#) (in Italian)

Starting from the artworks available in various Bologna's museums and libraries, this initiative intends to deconstruct, decolonise, integrate, the history of these artworks and collections with other stories involving other countries and cultures. The project aims to tell these stories by involving different artists (once per year) who will guide the audience through a free path inside museums, libraries, or important city places and bring it to the discovery of the city through its own - alternative point of view. The initiative is mainly addressed to young people under 35 as well as diasporic communities. The main focus of the initiative lies with:

- involving directly the participants in the re-enactment and enrichment of artistic and documentary narratives as well as Bologna's cultural heritage;
- raising awareness on the importance of knowledge and experience sharing;
- enhancing and facilitating cultural exchange between different communities.

[RomArchive](#)

"RomArchive, the Digital Archive of the Roma, makes arts and cultures of Roma visible, illustrating their contribution to European cultural history. Through narratives told by Roma themselves, RomArchive creates a reliable source of knowledge that is internationally accessible on the internet, thereby countering stereotypes and prejudices with facts."

Image from the Romarchive. Delaine Le Bas | poster | United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland | Oct. 9, 2008 - Oct. 30, 2008 | vis_00168. Rights held by: Delaine Le Bas | Licensed by: Delaine Le Bas | Licensed under: CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0 International | Provided by: Delaine Le Bas – Private Archive

The initiative focuses on the following approaches:

- making Romani culture and history more visible;
- setting **Roma voices** are at the centre of the project;
- overcoming/substituting prejudices about Roma through narratives and facts told by Roma themselves;
- having every aspect of the RomArchive created by following the principles of “Romani Leadership”: Roma were tasked with designing and defining the Archive;
- continuously **communicating** with the Roma community: content-related issues were regularly discussed during group’s meetings.

The action included the creation of a [Glossary](#) of Roma terms, a document in continuous evolution.

[Sinti and Roma in film history](#) (in German)

Romnokher is a Sinti and Roma small regional institution and cultural centre located in Oldenburg aiming at disseminating Sinti and Roma culture through exhibitions, research, and cultural initiatives. One of the research areas that is currently being explored comprehends detecting, flagging and explaining cinematographic stereotypes about Romani people.

[The Information and Documentation Centre for Anti-Racism Work e.V. \(IDA\)](#)

The IDA is a non-profit association founded on the initiative of several democratic youth organisations in the Federal Republic of Germany. The tasks of the IDA include the **provision**

of information on observations and developments as regards racism. The IDA collects information on the themes of counteracting racism, right-wing extremism, migration and society, anti-racist and intercultural openness, and diversity, and passes it on to interested individuals or organisations (mainly youth organisations, associations, initiatives, schools and multipliers in the field of youth work). In the context of the initiative, particular attention is given to the following actions:

- providing and maintaining information and documentation on the researched areas;
- giving advice during events, to those individuals interested in carrying on further research as well as to communities and youth associations;
- providing training through workshops, seminars, conferences;
- publishing reading material, newsletters, flyers that highlight the latest research results and initiatives;
- collaboration with external organisations and involvement in several networks and committees;

Within the context of its research, the institution created a [glossary](#) that aims at explaining in a brief and clear way key terms in the IDA research areas. The list is regularly updated.

[Bildungsstätte Anne Frank](#) (in German)

The Bildungsstätte Anne Frank is an educational centre located in Frankfurt but active throughout the whole nation built with the desire to sensitise young people and adults to issues such as racism, anti-semitism, homophobia, hate, etc., and to strengthen/encourage their active participation in an open, democratic society. The educational approach adopted by this institution is entirely focused on:

- organising workshops, training courses and interactive exhibitions where students, teachers and educators learn how to recognise current forms of anti-Semitism, racism and discrimination and what they can do about it;
- providing guidance and support to schools, clubs, associations, companies, museum and cultural institutions on how to deal with anti-semitism, populism and radicalisation;
- reaching a broad number of audience as well as enlarging their network through the planning of national events as well as through local initiatives involving social minorities, religious groups, communities;
- contributing to the current research through the critical examination of the history of National Socialism and Shoah as well as German colonial history;

[WEAVE: Methodological framework for community engagement](#)

The document was developed in the context of the WEAVE project (Widen European Access to cultural communities Via Europeana) and illustrates the **WEAVE methodological framework for community engagement** which is at the centre of the setup for capacity-building-oriented approaches at the basis of the collaboration between CHIs and cultural communities as well as the use of digital technologies to work and engage with intangible heritage content. The report offers reflections and shares experiences concerning

the organisation of community activities as well as guidelines concerning community engagement and management of safeguarding and disseminating communities. In the context of the WEAVE methodology development, a compact set of meaningful takeaways was produced concerning community engagement and management, materials for training, and considering the available tools for social transformation and negotiation strategies.

[Museums Association - Decolonising Practice](#)

The Decolonisation Guidance working group is an initiative established in the context of the Museums Association to guide and support the museum (and cultural) sector on how to bring decolonial practice into all areas of museum practice in the UK. On this basis a series of guidelines were produced which aimed at helping museums to recognise the rationale for decolonising their collections and at providing them with practical advice on how to take action and decolonise their practices. Also, the guidelines include tips on community engagement (e. g. how to interact with groups, how to engage people and collaborate with them etc.)? Interesting takeaways from the Decolonisation guidance include:

- questioning how 'things get done' or what constitutes 'quality outcomes'; be prepared to revise working practices if they create obstacles;
- building and engaging in equitable relationships where all groups are part of decision making, aims and ways of working;
- embedding values of transparency and fairness in all the institution's engagement with collaborators;
- recognising and removing barriers to collaborations.

[TOOLKIT: Connecting to Communities](#)

The Creative Museum project (2014-2017) was created in response to the need to provide training for museum professionals and their partners to accommodate a perceived shift in the dynamic of museum public programmes, where museums find themselves working collaboratively outside the sector, creating a new language of participation and engagement. The Community Engagement Toolkit for Museums was built in context of this initiative and intended to encourage museums professionals in implementing creative and innovative practices in their institutions on how to open up and engage with communities.

[Inclusive Terminology Glossary - Carissa Chew](#)

The Inclusive Terminology Glossary was created by Carissa Chew as part of her internship at the National Library of Scotland (2020-2021) and was further enriched after its publication via Google Drive through feedback, comments, and suggestions by scholars, cultural heritage professionals, and members of the communities that are represented in the glossaries.

The glossary aims to support CH professionals with the identification of discriminatory language and harmful material in archival collections, catalogues, educational resources, etc. Also, it intends to help CH professionals through:

1. the audit of catalogues, collections, and websites for discriminatory language and harmful material via (manual or automated) keyword searches;

2. the selection of non-discriminatory language when writing descriptions or creating resources;
3. the identification of discriminatory language and harmful material;
4. the location of materials relating to underrepresented histories, which might require the addition of information (i.e. subject headings or tags) to improve their discoverability;
5. the creation of user guidance on how to find materials relating to underrepresented histories, including recommended search terms;
6. the critical reflection on the use of internationally controlled vocabularies;
7. the equipment of cultural heritage professionals with the knowledge to respond to user inquiries relating to terminology and advise users on which search terms to use to discover materials related to underrepresented histories.

The glossary was edited in the framework of the National Library of Scotland's Equalities, Diversity, and Inclusion internship project, whose tasks and outcomes might be considered an interesting source of inspiration:

- research into the terminologies that have been used to describe groups with protected characteristics in the past;
- implementation of a sample of **suggested metadata changes**;
- exploration of the different ways through which cultural heritage institutions have chosen to warn users about the presence of harmful material and discriminatory language in their catalogues and collections, leading to discussions about an institutional statement on harmful material and discriminatory language;
- the establishment of an **internal Terminology Working Group**, a sub-group of the Metadata Steering Group, to manage and coordinate this area of descriptive and interpretive work;
- the **founding of a virtual network for professionals across the cultural heritage sector** to share their work and ideas about the management of EDI issues and descriptive and interpretive practice.

[NEMO Guidelines](#)

The NEMO (Network of European Museum Organisations) guidelines are designed to offer ideas and outline important factors for success in the area of education and public engagement in museums. *"The guidelines offer recommendations on how staff can develop and further professionalise education and public engagement at their museums independent of the size and organisational form of their respective museum. Many things can be implemented step-by-step which the audience will quickly appreciate."* They focus on key questions formulated from the perspective of museums, to help and further develop education and public engagement approaches and techniques in museums supporting them in opening up to diverse types of audiences as well as facilitating audience accessibility.

Emotion networking

The Emotion networking method provides insights into complicated interplays between emotions, interests and knowledge. It also helps to understand the relationship between cultural heritage and people, adding layers of complexity related to personal experiences and historical development. "The aim is for participants to notice changes in these relationships and to become (more) aware of the complex dynamics surrounding heritage." The expected results:

1. establishing a set of competencies that enable people to relate critically to processes of heritage making;
2. creating an open space for dialogue and collaborative knowledge sharing;
3. creating awareness of heritage dynamics;
4. increasing perception and respect for people's (and self) positionality;
5. helping people to deal with the past in the present, which is often emotionally charged.

ROUTES TO REFLECTION

Routes to reflection: proposed approach for DE-BIAS community work

In the scope of DE-BIAS, four consortium partners committed to designing a co-creation workflow with designated community groups. The groups were defined on the basis of pre-existing relationships of the partners with said communities, or their interest in establishing a collaboration. Furthermore, community groups were aligned with three main themes chosen for the DE-BIAS use case: migration & colonial past, gender & sexuality, ethnicity & ethnoreligious identity.

For the concrete piloting actions of the partners and their community groups, no fixed preliminary plans were imposed; we intently opted to have activities shaped through a continuous dialogue with community stakeholders, so as to ensure that not only the outcomes but also the process towards those outcomes would be the result of co-creation.

This 'elastic' approach doesn't imply that partners operated in a methodological vacuum. As meetings of a dedicated community engagement team, negotiations with community experts/allies and conversations with the external advisory board unfolded, the present methodology was compiled to provide frameworks and guidelines for co-design, as well as directionality and indicators for interaction.

With the preceding chapters furnishing the framework of our approach, the following sections will zoom in on our actions. First, the elements of a diligent, fair, reciprocal and balanced approach towards community engagement are laid out in a table. Secondly, three 'signposts' are highlighted, offering case-oriented suggestions and recommendations. The final chapter to this methodology will go on to reflect the workflows chosen and applied by the respective partners and their community groups.

Table of elements

The following table resulted from weighing the need to provide guidelines and markers to partners actively engaging with community groups against the key principle of leaving the methodology 'open' enough to include community co-steering in all stages of the collaboration. We envisaged this table to be a checklist for each partner to consider while co-designing the scenarios and schedules for their respective community activities. The ways in which each element needs to be addressed, are to be decided upon 'en route' with community groups and - as a crucial point of leverage - their experts/allies.

Starting a conversation			
What?	How?	Why?	The big picture
Contacts with allies , discussions, meetings	Introduce yourself	Establish a human, individual relationship	The community experts/allies ideally also become experts in/allies of the DE-BIAS project. This way, they can translate community needs and goals to the project team and vice versa. An important consideration: their role as bridge-builders is a crucial one that brings about many responsibilities and deep involvement. Therefore, we strongly recommend 1) frequent conversations with the experts/allies, through an open pipeline of (reciprocal) contact channels; 2) the thorough investigation of fair
	Introduce the project		
	Build trust through iterative contacts and foundational discussions; address problematic legacies such as historical power dynamics and invite experts/allies to help install an equilibrium rooted in equality.		
	Be clear about project and collaboration goals. Why does this project matter? How does it relate to the community? Why is this of importance towards this community's representation?		

	<p>Be clear about what we can offer: representation in cultural collections, remuneration</p>		<p>remuneration of the experts/allies; 3) the establishment of a collaborative relationship that functions as a gateway to future joint efforts</p>
<p>Describe the setup (all together with community allies)</p>	<p>Timeframe</p>		
	<p>Number of people</p>		
	<p>Background of people</p>		
	<p>Attempt to not pre-fix a full recipe - the recipe is made in and during your community interactions, with the ingredients that you bring to the table</p>		
	<p>The key ingredient is co-creation. As a core driver for your activity, please consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary or breakout group discussions on intercultural dialogue (with possible use of the DRIS dictionary - cfr. Signpost 1) 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An activity contributing to the DE-BIAS vocabulary (with possible use of existing vocabularies as an outset for ideation or a subject of validation) • A storytelling activity providing context for vocabulary entries, on the basis of digital/physical collections 		
	<p>We ideally suggest an iterative approach, unfolding through two or more engagement activities. A possible path is to disperse activities over the basic material to be explored:</p> <p>IMAGE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptions and self-expression <p>TEXT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stories about words > validation, devaluation, discussion about specific terms • Provide the context to the content 		

Consider -pre-surveying your participants	Pre-survey co-conducted with the experts/allies. A short questionnaire can help to highlight specific interests, key topics, potential barriers, previous experiences in similar initiatives, and expectations		
Meet participating communities	The who, when, where and how are decided upon together with experts/allies		
	Depending on the community needs and requirements, the format for an initial conversation is chosen: from a short project pitch with Q&A to a day-long workshop with hands-on activities		
	The opening of the community event should entail a compact revisitation of all the elements addressed with the experts/allies: project intro, including goals, importance, expectations, compensations, and modes of interaction		
The community group as a partner: continued journey	Share the activities' outcomes with the experts/allies and those		

	<p>community members who agreed to be contacted; give due credits, whether shared externally or internally</p>		
	<p>Keep the community informed about the rest of the project; invite community members to any public or significant project event</p>		
	<p>Involve those interested among community members into the technological part of the project: what is being developed, how can they contribute, and how will it in the end benefit the community?</p>		
	<p>Explore potential follow-up projects; try to co-imagine a future</p>		

Signposts for thoughtful engagement

Signpost 1: Nourish the intercultural dialogue

That words not only have the potential to hurt but also to connect and inspire, is a theme we thought to be important for our methodology. Any action towards de-biasing collections, data, metadata - even those powered by Artificial Intelligence - in the end comes down to establishing direct links between people. To create pipelines of conversation between collection holders and heritage communities allowing for the co-design of counter-strategies.

To support such conversations to take root, the exploration of positive and identity-affirming language is a recommended approach - tried and tested by the DE-BIAS team at an early stage of discussions about community work. Partner ECCOM pointed out a resource we found very useful: the Intercultural Alphabet. This collection of a variety of texts, along with the personal comments of those who participated in the [Art Clicks](#) and [DRIS](#) projects, address the issue of intercultural dialogue in the cultural field. Participants - who worked for cultural institutions and associations as well as social organisations - expressed visions, suggested proposals, identified the key features of intercultural dialogue in the form of keywords. These different expressions interweave among each other and the words that have been selected should be perceived as a polyphonic, collective endeavour, where the diversity of voices and expressions is safeguarded and valorised.

Words inspiring conversation

Among the words selected for the Intercultural Alphabet, some could be particularly interesting to frame the co-creative work which the DE-BIAS partners are about to start with local communities in order to detect possible biased words within the Europeana platform.

Access to culture: The right to take part in cultural life guarantees the right of everyone to access, participate in and enjoy culture, cultural heritage and cultural expressions. The full realisation of this right depends on concrete steps for the conservation, development, and diffusion of culture. It is defined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 27: 1. Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author. Human rights are inherent to all human beings, regardless of race, sex, nationality, ethnicity, language, religion, or any other status. They are individual and inalienable, protected by international law.

Ambiguphobia: is a term invented by the writer David Foster Wallace to describe the discomfort one feels in leaving something open for interpretation by others. It indicates the almost phobic reactivity in the face of the ambiguity created by the many definitions or interpretations used for a single concept and which end up being redundant rather than clarifying.

Common space: Art is the common language to bring differences together. In the "common space" of the museum – by definition, a protected environment – all potentially excluded publics find acceptance and the possibility of engaging in experiences of narration in the presence of the regular museum public. This is how the museum fits positively into the difficult path of integration of the so-called "non-public", making itself the interpreter of a profound need: to escape the conditions of marginality and isolation and to seek an identity through participation in cultural life.

Contact zones: defined by Jerome Clifford in 1997 as places for exchange and the development of new relations based on mutual recognition.

Cultural democracy: The concept comprises a set of related commitments: protecting and promoting cultural diversity, and the right to culture for everyone; encouraging active participation in community cultural life; enabling people to participate in policy decisions; and ensuring fair and equitable access to cultural resources. It sustains the idea that everyone has rights that deserve respect and must have a voice in the vital decisions that affect the quality of our lives. It expresses the tension between cultural democratisation, understood as making elite art more attractive, towards more challenging ideas of cultural democracy which recognises culture as the diverse, multipolar creation of all social groups, and a human right. In light of the above, cultural democracy and democratisation of culture should both serve a coherent political system and its sovereignty structures by overcoming the underlying ambiguity in the concept of "democratisation of culture" whereby public policies are intended to promote access to culture and not necessarily initiation to culture (active participation) which needs mediation and education policies to reduce the hurdles for a fulfilling experience. Cultural democracy is therefore about learning to understand, interpret, recreate; but also, about participating individually and collectively to cultural life and decision-making of cultural policies and programs as an active citizen.

Edge effect: is a concept we borrow from ecology in order to describe the features of the areas where two different ecosystems meet, and a third one is born with new characteristics. For example, when the desert meets the savannah in Africa, or when the fresh waters of the Amazon mix with the Atlantic Ocean's saltwater, new forms of life develop, benefiting from the intake of two merging systems. Likewise, when two different cultures meet in social systems, they create a mixture, new peoples, new civilisations, intersections, exchanges which in some cases generate refusal, exclusion, conflict, abuse of power, violence, intolerance: in contrast to what happens in nature, a resistance, a defence mechanism are introduced with the aim of preserving the status quo. The willingness to encounter different cultures opens up unpredictable scenarios, unexpected resources that in other moments of history gave birth to "cultural metissage": a model of cohabitation which is different from the individual systems merged into it.

Empathy: in an increasingly arid and less and less human world, we must find the strength to direct our gaze towards others, and rediscover emotional intelligence and the ability to

empathise. In an historic moment in which we are used to reacting by judging and accusing, we must find curiosity and understanding about what surrounds us.

Evidence of uncertainty/risk: risk avoidance can be defined as the environment in which members of a culture fear uncertainty and the occurrence of unknown situations. In cultures where risk avoidance has low scores, uncertainty is considered a normal feature of life and every day is accepted as it is; children are taught that what is different is intriguing, teachers can say "don't I know", and there is a certain tolerance of deviant ideas and behaviours. In cultures where risk avoidance has high scores, life uncertainty is considered a constant threat to be fought, children are taught that what is different is dangerous, teachers must always have all the answers and the general tendency is towards the suppression of deviant ideas and behaviours.

Motivation: in intercultural projects, and in general with cultural activity, it is important to be clear about the urgency that drives us to propose and carry out the project, as well as the needs that one will encounter, in order not to risk entering into a dynamic of appropriation of the other and a sterile confirmation of what exists.

Pan-human: Rob Redfield, in the 1957 conference "The universally human and the culturally variable", provided a tool, that is still useful today, for reading how culture is stratified over time and how it can inform different levels. The Redfield strategy is actually very useful for distinguishing the ways in which we can think about culture, and for the different dimensions that are recognised in this concept. It puts on the same horizontal axis the contrasting modes of thinking and acting that are biologically inherited (Hereditary) with those acquired through the course of life experience (Acquired), which then encounter three ways of "thinking about oneself in the world": separately, as individuals (defined as individual or idiosyncratic); within community or society, that is, within one's own group or public of reference; and together with all human beings, that is, in the world as a person and with all people (this level is known as the Universal or pan-human scheme). The intersections created by the juncture of these elements represent different conceptions of understanding human nature. Pan-human is what should be applied to activate intercultural processes, departing from a point of view that allows us to conceive of ourselves as members of humanity.

Privilege: the intercultural relationship cannot ignore an analysis of the position from which one engages.

Recognising (not denying): the need to categorise is part of human nature. It is exactly from this process that prejudices arise. Each of us, by nature, therefore has prejudices. To be predisposed to the encounter with others, we must recognise which of them are ours, understand them and try to unhinge them, precisely by coming into contact with the object of our prejudice.

Retrotopia: with this term, Bauman describes the partly wistful quest for a past status quo as opposed to the search for the new which is inherent in Utopia. Retrotopia means looking to the past so as to be reassured about an uncertain, troublesome future, where our comfort zones seem threatened by an increasingly diverse world and competing models. A favourable

environment in which we can act, secure resources and identify goals in a way that makes us feel safe.

Sociability: although connected with the realm of empathy, this term merely implies we are able to mutually acknowledge the wounds of experience. It is not the same as actively getting closer to the Other, as acting together, but is the reciprocal awareness of a bond, a connection allowing us to preserve a sense of humanity. Everyone is aware of the others; social interaction sometimes happens in our minds, side by side without talking or touching. This is the step leading from the universal pleasure of friendliness to a condition of sociability. The French term "sociabilité" denotes the sense of security we need to cope with delicate or hostile social situations. It is a socially competent behaviour in difficult conditions which is deeply settled, rather than the result of occasional impressions; it is the so-called *savoir-faire* guiding our behaviour.

Third space: the added value given by intercultural planning is that of being able to create a third space in which all the subjectivities involved can be transformed through the encounter. Rather than continually thematise identity, difference, and making intercultural practice a mirror upon which "interculture" is reflected, co-planning can actually be the moment of creation for a new language that emerges from the specificities of each individual, and then surpasses them.

Trust: can be understood as one of the many opposites of fear, a dangerously widespread attitude in our society. Instrumentalising fear is easy because it is composed of a myriad of different facets: fear of the foreigner, fear of terrorism, fear of the economic crisis, fear of every unknown man when I walk alone at night on the street. As soon as any aspect of this "great fear" engages in our minds, it takes very little to make room for the acceptance of security, repressive or nationalist policies. We are comforted by the illusion that if we gather in our homes, behind brick walls and masks of indifference we will finally be safe among equals. The importance of maintaining a positive, favourable, and trusting attitude in the encounter with the other thus becomes a political tool to affirm the refusal to live in fear, to renounce one's individual liberties and the desire to explore the world in the name of security.

But trusting also means starting from the assumption that there is something that equates people despite all their possible differences. This "common humanity" becomes the basis from which to begin: to think that everyone deserves the equivalent of what I hope for myself and my loved ones; that rights, freedoms, and wellbeing are not a luxury for the privileged few; that all the people in front of me are artists or scientists "in power"... Recognising our common humanity and the human potential of each of us is not only a useful interpretative tool to learn about and relate to differences, but it can become a starting point to formulate inclusive and supportive political strategies.

Signpost 2: Community pivots

In the DE-BIAS project, the goal is to address the harmful use of language in metadata related to digital cultural collections, with a focus on engaging with marginalised communities. Given

the potential for exposure to biased language and the risk of causing trauma to community members, it is essential to adopt a sensitive and respectful approach. This section of the DE-BIAS Methodology outlines the rationale for working with community allies and provides recommendations for selecting appropriate allies and establishing meaningful and considerate interactions with them.

Rationale for working with community allies

Community allies are crucial intermediaries who facilitate respectful and effective engagement with communities. These allies, including researchers, cultural professionals, educators, and civil society representatives, possess the expertise and empathy necessary to bridge the gap between project teams and the communities they aim to serve. Involving community allies helps in:

- The rationale for involving community allies includes several key points. Direct exposure to biased language in collection descriptions can be distressing for community members, so allies act as buffers, reviewing content and guiding the project's communication to minimise potential harm. They often have a deep understanding of the cultural nuances and historical contexts of the communities they represent, which enables them to provide valuable insights into respectful language use and cultural representation.
- Engaging with community allies helps build trust with minoritised communities because allies who are respected within their communities can vouch for the project's integrity, fostering a collaborative and trusting relationship. Additionally, allies can help translate the technical language of digital collections into terms that are meaningful and accessible to community members. This ensures clear and effective communication, enhancing community engagement and participation.
- By involving allies, the project empowers communities to take an active role in shaping the vocabulary and metadata used to describe their heritage. This involvement promotes a sense of ownership and agency over their cultural representations. In summary, community allies play a vital role in mitigating harm and trauma, enhancing cultural sensitivity, building trust and credibility, facilitating effective communication, and supporting community empowerment.

Examples of community allies

All of the DE-BIAS project partners involved in community activities have done so through the involvement of community allies, the range of which demonstrates the diversity of potential collaborations and their impact. KU Leuven partnered with Professor Donatien Dibwé dia Mwembu for community events focused on storytelling about colonial heritage and worked with Congolese Kring, an organisation dedicated to improving the cultural position and visibility of the Congolese diaspora in Belgium. The European Fashion Heritage Association collaborated with Queering Rome and the Victoria & Albert Museum's Terminology Working Group. DFF - Deutsches Filminstitut & Filmmuseum engaged via Lea Wohl von Haselberg with

the Jewish Cultural Studies research community in Potsdam and Frankfurt to support the creation and validation of the DE-BIAS vocabulary. The Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision worked with the Surinamese community via Sharma Soerjoesing-Chin A Foeng, a producer and presenter at Omroep West. Sharma facilitated co-creation sessions and established connections between the institute and members of the Dutch Surinamese community.

Recommendations for selecting and engaging with community allies

To ensure successful collaboration, it is important to select community allies who are well-positioned to represent and support the communities in question. The following recommendations propose considerations for reaching out to allies and establishing meaningful and considerate interactions with them:

- **Identify Individuals with strong community ties:** Select allies who have established, trusted relationships within their communities. They are more likely to be seen as legitimate representatives and can effectively advocate for the community's interests.
- **Choose allies with relevant expertise:** Look for allies who possess knowledge and experience in areas relevant to the project, such as cultural heritage, community advocacy, and education. Their expertise will enhance the project's ability to address issues under discussion in a culturally sensitive manner.
- **Prioritise allies with a commitment to social justice:** Allies who are dedicated to promoting equity and social justice are more likely to understand the importance of topics such as addressing biased language in cultural metadata and can provide valuable perspectives on inclusive practices.
- **Ensure diverse representation:** Select allies who reflect the diversity within the minoritised communities. This includes considering factors such as age, gender, socioeconomic background, and different sub-communities to ensure a comprehensive and representative approach.
- **Establish clear and respectful communication protocols:** Develop guidelines for communication and collaboration that prioritise respect, transparency, and mutual understanding. This includes setting expectations for regular updates, feedback mechanisms, and conflict resolution strategies.

To foster a productive and respectful relationship with community allies, it is important to adhere to a number of key principles. Engaging in active listening by showing genuine interest in the perspectives and experiences of community allies demonstrates respect and helps build trust. It is essential to acknowledge and value the contributions of community allies, ensuring they feel appreciated for their expertise and efforts. Providing adequate support and resources, such as relevant information, tools, and training, enables allies to participate effectively. Promoting collaborative decision-making by involving community allies in the project's decision-making processes ensures their insights and recommendations are integrated into project outcomes. Lastly, maintaining cultural sensitivity and awareness by being mindful of cultural differences and the potential impact of language and actions is

crucial. Showing respect for cultural norms and practices and being open to learning from the community allies' knowledge and experiences further strengthens the relationship.

Signpost 3: Follow-up, feedback and give back

A key component of respectful, meaningful, sustainable, value-driven, and ethically consistent community engagement is the diligent follow-up with community members after core activities, such as workshops, have concluded. This chapter outlines the importance of treating the community group as a partner in an ongoing journey, detailing how to share outcomes, maintain communication, involve community members in project developments, and explore future collaborations.

Sharing outcomes and giving due credits

After the completion of core activities, it is essential to share the outcomes with both the community allies and those community members who agreed to be contacted. This transparent dissemination of results ensures that all participants are aware of the impact and contributions of their involvement. Furthermore, giving due credits to these individuals, whether shared externally or internally, acknowledges their valuable input and fosters a sense of appreciation and recognition within the community.

Keeping the community informed

Maintaining regular communication with the community is vital for fostering a long-term partnership. Keeping the community informed about the project's progress, milestones, and developments is crucial. This can be achieved through newsletters, updates on the project website, or direct communication channels. Additionally, inviting community members to public or significant project events helps to maintain their engagement and reinforces their importance as stakeholders in the project.

Involving community members in other project areas

Involving interested community members in other aspects of a project - e.g. technology development, policy work, strategic discussions - can enhance their sense of ownership and contribution. Informing them about what is being developed, how they can contribute, and how the final outcomes will benefit the community ensures that they remain engaged and motivated. This involvement can include workshops, beta testing of new tools, or advisory roles in the technological development process.

Express openness to future collaborations

Exploring potential follow-up projects and co-imagining a future in which new collaborations can root is a crucial aspect of sustainable engagement. By brainstorming and planning future initiatives together, the project can build on the foundation of trust and cooperation established during the initial activities. This forward-thinking approach not only ensures continuity but also fosters innovation and deeper connections between the project team and the community.

IN CONCLUSION

Closing the loop: communities and cultural heritage as a common good

An epilogue by Cristina Da Milano (ECCOM)

The relationship between heritage and communities implies the need for a clear binary vision of community members as active subjects and not just passive recipients of cultural policies, actions and strategies. The already mentioned Faro Convention is still a milestone for the understanding of the role of cultural heritage in contemporary society: starting from the concept that the use of cultural heritage falls between the rights of the individual to come into the cultural life of the community and enjoy the arts, as enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the Faro Convention represents a step forward since it grants to the populations to play an active role in recognizing the values of cultural heritage and invites States to promote participatory processes, based on the synergy between public institutions, private citizens, associations.

The main element of novelty of the Faro Convention is constituted precisely by the shift of attention from the object - cultural heritage - to the subject, citizens and community: art. 12 of the Convention in fact affirms that the parties undertake to "take into consideration the value attributed by each patrimonial community to the cultural heritage in which it identifies" and "to promote actions to improve access to cultural heritage, in particular for young people and disadvantaged people, in order to raise awareness of its value, the need to conserve and preserve it and the benefits that can derive from it"³⁴.

The Faro Convention therefore sees in the participation of citizens and communities the key to an increased awareness in Europe about the value of cultural heritage and its contribution to well-being and quality of life.

The key points are the notion of cultural heritage as a common good; the definition of "community of inheritance" and the concept of value as something socially constructed.

Regarding the first point, the term "common good" describes a specific good that is shared and beneficial for everyone - or for the most part - of the members of a given community. This also applies to cultural heritage that ultimately belongs to humanity and is preserved for future generations. Water, air, environment are common goods in a global sense, but the historic centre of a city, a monument, a local museum, a public garden, a landscape, are goods that benefit specific communities and can be key elements of local development, helping to improve the quality of life of that community and producing integration, social cohesion, and sense of belonging.

The second point concerns "heritage communities", which the Convention defines as "a group of people who attribute value to specific aspects of cultural heritage, and who wish, in the

³⁴ *Ibid.*

framework of public action, to support them and pass them on to future generations"³⁵. It is clear that the concept of community can be understood in a broader sense, but it is anyway closely linked to the notions of access, participation and representation.

As for the third point, communities play a fundamental role in the valorisation of heritage, since - through participatory processes - they consciously appropriated the values connected to it, redefining them: in fact, the concept of value is socially constructed and changes over time, depending on historical, social and cultural factors. A further strengthening of this concept passes through the UNESCO Recommendation of 2015, in which cultural heritage is defined as a set of material and immaterial values recognised by the populations, key actors of the processes of identifying what heritage is³⁶.

Promoting not only access but also participation in activities related to heritage and decision-making processes and the representation of communities means, in a word, to seriously invest in processes of community engagement, conceived as strategic assets that allow cultural organisations to put the public - conceived not only as visitors but as individuals and communities of reference - at the centre of their action: they need to invest in opening-up participation to decision-making processes, and fostering representation, through which it is possible to complete the vision of the Faro Convention.

The strategies on which to focus in order to achieve results are those promoted by DE-BIAS and related to: processes of co-creation; internal and external capacity building (intended to strengthen the capacity of internal staff and communities); collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data (on the motivations that push individuals / communities); partnerships with different stakeholders; use of new technologies.

Beyond the strategic elements, there are new frontiers that we - as the DE-BIAS project partners and as cultural professionals - have in front of us: first of all, we are facing the hard task of breaking the borders (not only between people but also between disciplines), making them areas of contact, safe places for debating and discussing burning issues³⁷, anchoring them to values such as inclusion, dialogue and interdisciplinarity and re-reading the values traditionally associated with heritage in a post-structuralist key. This is clearly the only possible way to be able to reconcile a value system based on the contrast between "Us" and "Them" with one based, in a word, on the concept of sustainability. Moreover, we need to keep on reflecting on the concept of community, trying to overcome a contradiction inherent in the Faro Convention: if it is true that the Convention establishes the link between the value of heritage and community, this does not help us to overcome the dichotomous vision "we"

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ UNESCO, [*Recommendation concerning the protection and promotion of museums and collections, their diversity and their role in society*](#), Paris, 2015.

³⁷ M. Vlachou, "Dividing issues and mission-driven activism", in R.R. James and R. Sandell (eds.) *Museum Activism*, Londra, Routledge 2019, pp. 47-57.

and "the others", if the community itself perceives itself as a closed, given, immobile, scarcely permeable system.

The only way to affirm and turn into practice the processual, inclusive and dynamic value of cultural heritage from a post-structuralist point of view is to recognise, sustain and reverse those same values as values of the community, as the DE-BIAS project is doing, also through the development and the dissemination of a document such as this one. This osmosis between individual, community and heritage - conceived as open systems - is the only feasible way to achieve the objective of sustainability, not only conceived in its economic and environmental but also in its social and cultural dimensions.

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